

**CARBON
FARMING MED**

**Interreg
Euro-MED**

Co-funded by
the European Union

September 2025

REPORT ON EXTERNALITIES TO BE INCLUDED IN CARBON CREDITS

<https://carbonfarmingmed.interreg-euro-med.eu/>

Deliverable 1.6.1. Report on externalities to be included in carbon credits

Project acronym	CARBON FARMING MED
Project title	Accelerating Carbon Market Development for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Mediterranean agriculture
Project mission	Strengthening and innovative sustainable economy
Project priority	Greener MED
Specific objective	RSO2.6: Promoting the transition to a circular and resource efficient economy
Type of project	Test project (Thematic Project)
Project duration	January 2024–September 2026 (33 months)

Deliverable title	Report on externalities to be included in carbon credits
Deliverable number	1.6.1.
Deliverable type	Report
Work package number	WP 1
Work package title	Carbon farming framework in the Mediterranean
Activity name	Carbon farming positive externalities
Activity number	1.6
Partner in charge (author)	Center for Energy, Environment and Resources- Cener 21
Partners involved	CREA, EURAF, UVIC-UCC

Document history

Versions	Date	Document status	Delivered by
Version 1.0	08/09/2025	Draft	CENER 21
Version 2.0	18/09/2025	Comments from PP	PP
Version 3.0	30/09/2025	Final	CENER 21

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Abbreviations

CF	Carbon farming
CFPs	Carbon farming practices
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
MED	Mediterranean
NBS	Nature-based solution
RegenAg	Regenerative Agriculture
ROI	Return on Investment
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon

Executive summary

This report presents a comprehensive assessment of carbon farming practices in Mediterranean contexts, combining an extensive review of scientific literature with primary data collected from farms actively implementing these practices. The evaluation integrates economic, environmental, and social dimensions, supported by the “1.6 Database on Carbon Farming,” which provides a systematic scoring of literature and case studies. Primary farm-level data offer practical insights into the real-world performance, feasibility, and adoption drivers of carbon farming measures. Findings confirm that carbon farming delivers substantial economic benefits, including improved yield stability, reduced input costs, and access to higher-value markets. Social benefits are evident in strengthened rural livelihoods, improved knowledge exchange, and increased community resilience to economic and climatic challenges. Environmental benefits, the most extensively documented, include higher soil organic carbon stocks, improved soil structure and fertility, strengthened biodiversity in the agrosystems, increased water retention, and enhanced climate resilience. The report also identifies notable gaps in current knowledge, particularly in the consistent measurement of economic and social co-benefits, reflecting a lack of standardized indicators and long-term monitoring. The report emphasizes the high potential of carbon farming as a multi-benefit strategy in the Mediterranean, its relevance for EU Green Deal objectives and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), and the need for targeted research, supportive policies, and integration of co-benefits into carbon credit frameworks to enhance the value, credibility, and market adoption of these practices.

Key words: Carbon farming, Mediterranean agriculture, Sustainable agriculture, Co-benefits, Climate resilience

1. Introduction

This report provides a structured assessment of the **positive externalities- environmental, economic, and social**, associated with the implementation of carbon farming practices. It aims to support **evidence-based decision-making** and guide the **large-scale adoption of sustainable agricultural systems** by providing robust insight into how carbon farming contributes not only to carbon sequestration, but also to broader climate, economic, and societal objectives.

The primary focus of the report is to **identify and evaluate externalities and co-benefits¹** that should be systematically incorporated into the valuation and recognition of carbon credits. While carbon sequestration remains a central pillar of carbon farming, a growing body of evidence demonstrates that regenerative practices (including the agroforestry system in the MED zone) deliver a wide range of additional outcomes, many of which remain insufficiently captured within existing credit methodologies. By expanding the lens beyond emission reduction alone, this report seeks to contribute to the development of more **comprehensive, transparent, and inclusive carbon credit frameworks**.

The **environmental section** of the report focuses on how carbon farming practices improve agroecological conditions through enhanced soil health, increased soil organic carbon, improved water retention, and biodiversity conservation. Special emphasis is placed on the role of carbon farming in climate change mitigation and adaptation, highlighting how nature-based solutions (NBS's) strengthen resilience to droughts, temperature extremes, and land degradation processes.

The **economic section** explores the contribution of carbon farming to the financial viability of agricultural systems. It assesses how regenerative practices affect input costs, productivity, and market positioning, with a particular focus on yield stability, reduction in chemical and energy inputs, and access to premium value chains and eco-certified markets. The section also addresses transition-related costs and the long-term profitability potential of carbon farming systems.

The **social section** addresses the broader societal benefits of carbon farming, including its impact on rural livelihoods, employment, knowledge transfer, food security, and community well-being. Particular attention is given to how carbon farming can enhance community-level resilience. It also highlights the current lack of systematic inclusion of social dimensions in carbon market mechanisms and proposes pathways for better integration.

¹In carbon farming it is possible to distinguish two types of outcomes:

Co-benefits are intended and direct effects, such as improved soil fertility, crop yields and productivity, water retention, increase of soil organic carbon alongside carbon sequestration.

Positive externalities are indirect, unplanned benefits that often extend beyond the farm, such as enhanced biodiversity, reduced GHG emissions, erosion control, or improved ecosystem health.

Throughout the report, **primary data from farms applying carbon farming practices** are interwoven with **secondary data from existing research and scientific literature**. Together, these complementary sources offer valuable insights into the real-world effects and broader implications of carbon farming, reinforcing the evidence base for the inclusion of externalities in carbon credit valuation.

By presenting this three-pillar analysis, the **Report on Externalities to be Included in Carbon Credits** provides a strategic foundation for enhancing the credibility, transparency, and market relevance of carbon credit systems. It emphasizes that formally recognizing environmental, economic, and social co-benefits within carbon credit methodologies is not only a matter of fairness or scientific accuracy, but a pragmatic step toward unlocking the full value of carbon farming in the transition to sustainable agriculture and climate resilience.

The report proposes that integrating these co-benefits into carbon credit valuation frameworks allows for the development of **high-integrity credits** that better reflect the **true multidimensional impact of regenerative practices**. Such credits have the potential to attract a broader range of investors and buyers, particularly those aligned with Environmental, social, and governance (ESG) principles, sustainable supply chains, and global climate and biodiversity targets.

Furthermore, this approach enhances the differentiation and marketability of carbon credits generated through carbon farming by recognizing their contribution to public goods that are currently undervalued, such as rural employment, soil regeneration, food system resilience, and ecosystem services. By embedding these elements into valuation systems, the report supports the evolution of carbon markets from a narrow focus on emission reduction to a more holistic instrument for sustainable development and environmental justice.

Ultimately, this report calls for a paradigm shift, from treating carbon as a single commodity to viewing carbon farming as a platform for delivering **systemic transformation in land use, agricultural management, economy, and society**. Grounded in the Mediterranean context it provides guidance for policymakers, standard-setters, and market actors seeking to design robust, inclusive, and high-impact carbon credit mechanisms that are fit for purpose in a rapidly changing world.

2. Determination of co-benefits to assess

Co-benefits refer to the **additional environmental, economic, and social benefits** generated through the application of regenerative agricultural practices. While the climate mitigation role of carbon sequestration is well-established, the inclusion of co-benefits offers a **more holistic understanding of the real value of carbon farming**, particularly in the Mediterranean context, where farms are often exposed to climate, resource, and socio-economic stressors.

The co-benefits to be assessed are categorized into three main areas:

Environmental benefits: These include improvements in biodiversity, soil health, water retention, and a reduced reliance on chemical inputs, all contributing to the sustainability of agricultural ecosystems.

Economic benefits: CF can lead to increased crop yields, lower input costs, and the creation of additional revenue streams from carbon credits or certification schemes that incentivize sustainable practices.

Social benefits: The social impact of CF encompasses job creation, enhanced food security, and rural development, all contributing to the overall well-being of farming communities.

An evidence-informed shortlist of co-benefits was developed from a review of **scientific literature, technical reports, and case studies**, prioritising outcomes that are **significant, measurable, and context-relevant**. Stakeholder inputs from farmers and agricultural experts were incorporated to validate and contextualise the findings, ensuring the listed benefits are observed in practice and capturing under-reported outcomes (e.g., improved community collaboration, reduced financial stress). The resulting set provides the basis for a comprehensive evaluation of carbon-farming externalities, highlighting climate impacts alongside environmental, economic, and social contributions and supporting multi-criteria decision-making at farm, programme, and policy levels.

The agricultural practices that qualify as carbon farming activities and have been subject to analysis are organized into the following categories:

Use of organic amendments: Application of compost, manure, biochar, anaerobic digestate, and other organic materials to enhance soil carbon content.

Reducing soil disturbance: Implementation of minimum tillage, zero tillage, or reduced tillage systems.

Cover crops: Growing cover crops as green manure or mulch to protect soil and add organic matter.

Agroforestry practices: Establishing silvoarable systems, silvopastoral systems, hedgerows, and other tree-based farming practices.

Agronomic management: Practices such as intercropping, improved crop rotations, conservation agriculture, organic farming, and utilization of crop residues.

Conversion to perennial crops: Transitioning annual crops to perennial woody plantations like orchards, vineyards, olives, poplars, or other woody plantations and reforestation efforts.

Sustainable water management: Employing keyline design, moisture monitoring, terraces, and other techniques to improve water use efficiency.

The practices identified not only have the potential to sequester carbon but also offer significant co-benefits that align with the environmental and socio-economic goals of the Mediterranean region.

3. Methodological approach

The approach integrates three components:

- 1.Literature Review-** A curated database of 100 peer-reviewed and grey literature sources was developed and assessed against standardized criteria to identify key co-benefits. Additional materials as project evaluations, case studies, and strategic reports, expanded the scope.
- 2.Farmer Survey-** Primary data were collected via a survey targeting Mediterranean farmers engaged in carbon farming. The survey captured farmer-reported outcomes and perceptions of practice-related benefits.
- 3.Pilot Farms Data Analysis-** Soil data from project pilot farms were analyzed to assess changes in key indicators, including soil organic carbon (SOC) and nutrient levels.

This mixed-methods approach integrates **quantitative measures** (e.g., % SOC increase, input cost reduction) and **qualitative insights** (e.g., farmer experience) to triangulate findings. Methodological limitations, such as self-reporting bias, site heterogeneity, and limited data availability, are addressed in later chapters.

3.1. Literature review

The comprehensive literature review aimed to identify, classify, and analyse the positive externalities of carbon farming practices based on peer-reviewed scientific literature. The primary objective was to develop a robust **evidence base** that would inform the assessment of environmental, economic, and social co-benefits to be potentially recognized within carbon credit certification schemes. To ensure analytical consistency and thematic relevance, a clear set of inclusion and exclusion criteria was developed for the literature review process (Figure 1). The review was conducted using Google Scholar and Scopus databases.

Specific query-lines:

("Carbon Farming" AND ("Co-benefits" OR "externalities") AND Mediterranean)

("Regenerative Agriculture" AND Mediterranean AND ("Co-benefits" OR "externalities"))

(Agroforestry AND Mediterranean AND ("Co-benefits" OR "externalities"))

("Soil Organic Carbon" AND Mediterranean AND ("Co-benefits" OR "externalities"))

("Sustainable Agriculture" AND Mediterranean AND ("Co-benefits" OR "externalities"))

were applied. A complete database of the reviewed publications is provided in Annex 1- List of Publications Included in the Database.

Figure 1. Literature review methodology and criteria

3.1.1. Database Design and Comparative Analysis

Each reviewed study was recorded in a centralized database using a standardized format to ensure comparability. The database included core bibliographic information such as full **APA citation, study title, authorship, publication year**, and **source link** to facilitate traceability and reference verification.

Key content descriptors were also captured, including a **summary of the study's main conclusions**, with a focus on the effectiveness of carbon farming practices and the specific co-benefits identified. The **geographical context** of each study was recorded to account for regional environmental variables influencing outcomes, such as **topography, precipitation, temperature ranges, soil texture, SOC levels**, and **land-use history**.

Methodological aspects were documented, including both the specific **techniques** applied and their classification into **broader methodological groups**, allowing structured comparison and identification of best practices. Reported **benefits** were categorized as environmental, economic, or social. For each identified co-benefit, a **corresponding indicator**, quantitative or qualitative was noted, enabling precise evaluation of the outcomes.

Empirical results were extracted to support evidence-based assessment. To facilitate cross-study comparison, each co-benefit was assigned a **standardized grade (1-5)** based on internal evaluation criteria. **Justification** for the assigned grade was recorded in an accompanying comment field to contextualize the scoring and capture any relevant study-specific insights.

The layout and structure of the database are provided in Annex 2- Structure of the Database and Included Categories.

This approach enabled a transparent and comparable synthesis of findings across a diverse set of sources, supporting robust identification of recurring patterns and context-specific outcomes.

3.1.2. Synthesis and Gap Analysis

Following data structuring, a comparative analysis was conducted to identify **recurring co-benefits**, **contextual variables**, and **evidence patterns** across studies.

Frequently reported co-benefits included enhanced soil health, biodiversity improvement, and yield stability. These outcomes were consistently associated with practices such as organic amendments, cover cropping, and agroforestry.

Observed outcomes varied by environmental factors, including soil type, topography, precipitation, and baseline SOC. Such variability is critical for evaluating the applicability of results to Mediterranean agroecological conditions.

The database integrated both quantitative indicators (e.g., % increase in SOC, yield metrics) and qualitative data (e.g., farmer-reported livelihood changes), providing a multidimensional evidence base.

Several **gaps** emerged:

Environmental co-benefits dominate literature; economic and especially social impacts are underrepresented.

Mediterranean-specific studies remain limited, affecting the contextual relevance of global findings.

Co-benefits such as biodiversity gains and ecosystem resilience lack standardized indicators, hindering comparability and integration into crediting frameworks.

The structured review was limited to 100 studies (Annex 1- List of Publications Included in the Database) focused on carbon farming and co-benefits relevant to Mediterranean contexts. While this regional focus enhances applicability, it may overlook valuable evidence from other settings.

To address this, additional studies from non-Mediterranean regions were reviewed outside the formal database and used to triangulate and broaden the analytical perspective.

3.1.3. Key Insights for Application

The final step of the review involved extracting strategic insights to guide subsequent phases of analysis and inform integration with primary data. The analysis identified carbon farming practices that consistently delivered co-benefits across diverse agroecological settings. By linking observed co-benefits to their potential contribution to carbon credit value, the review supports a more holistic crediting logic that accounts for ecosystem and social benefits alongside carbon sequestration. The synthesized literature provided a comparative reference point for evaluating empirical data from pilot farms in Mediterranean regions, enhancing the contextual robustness of later findings.

3.2. Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits

To complement the literature review, a structured survey (Annex 3 - Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits) was conducted to gather primary data from farmers actively implementing carbon farming practices in the Mediterranean region. The objective was to capture first-hand observations of environmental, economic, and social co-benefits, providing context-specific insights for diverse agroecological settings. The survey targeted farms in the MED region (France, Spain, Italy, Greece, Croatia, and Bosnia and Herzegovina), ensuring representation across varied climates, soil types, and production systems. This geographic spread strengthened the relevance and applicability of the findings for Mediterranean conditions. The survey was organized into six sections, each addressing a key analytical dimension (Table 1).

Table 1. Structure of the Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits

Section	Key Focus Areas
A: Farm and Farmer Profile	Geographic location, farm size, production type, farmer's role, education, gender
B: Carbon Farming Practices Implemented	Adoption of practices such as composting, cover cropping, agroforestry, reduced tillage, water management, etc.
C: Perceived Environmental Co-Benefits	Soil health, biodiversity, water retention, reduction in synthetic inputs
D: Perceived Economic Co-Benefits	Yield variation, cost efficiency, market access, additional income (e.g., credits, labels)

E: Perceived Social Co-Benefits	Employment generation, intergenerational cooperation, food security, quality of life
F: Barriers, Motivations, and Recommendations	Institutional support, access to knowledge, perceived challenges, motivation for CF adoption

A total of 120 farmers actively implementing carbon farming practices across Mediterranean countries were invited to participate in the survey. Only seven completed surveys were received, resulting in a low response rate and limiting the representativeness of the sample. While this restricts the ability to draw generalizable conclusions, the responses provided valuable qualitative insights into on-farm experiences, perceived co-benefits, and implementation challenges. These findings were used to complement the literature review and provide practice-based perspectives that enrich the overall analysis.

3.3. Insights from pilot farms

To evaluate soil health and carbon storage under different management systems, soil data were analyzed from three pilot farms in Catalonia, Spain, within Work Package 2 (WP2). Each farm included plots under conventional and regenerative practices, enabling comparisons within farms and across locations. The dataset covered key parameters relevant to carbon farming (Figure 2). Laboratory analyses were performed for soil chemistry and physical properties; SOC stock and climate data were derived from spatial datasets. The values for temperature, precipitation, and SOC stock were derived from map-based data sources. In contrast, all other soil parameters (e.g., total carbon, nitrogen, bulk density, pH, texture) were obtained through laboratory analysis of collected soil samples.

Figure 2. Framework of Analyzed Key Factors and Constraints in Pilot Farms

The methodological framework and its inherent limitations provide important context for the interpretation of the data. With these considerations established, the following section focuses on assessing the positive externalities of carbon farming practices, exploring their environmental, social, and economic impacts.

4. Review of externalities to be included in carbon credit

The assessment of co-benefits draws on three evidence streams: (4.1) a structured review of 100 publications, (4.2) a Mediterranean farmer survey, and (4.3) pilot farm soil data from Catalonia. Together, these sources provide environmental, economic, and social insights that support the inclusion of multiple co-benefits in carbon credit valuation.

4.1. Literature review and evaluation of carbon farming positive externalities

The literature review was based on a structured database of 100 scientific and technical publications covering 126 regions. Studies were published between 2015 and 2025, with 2020 showing the highest output (16 studies) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Distribution of scientific publications in the database by year of publication

Because the report focuses on Mediterranean conditions, two contexts were considered:

- **Mediterranean basin countries** (22 nations bordering the Mediterranean Sea, including Italy, Spain, Greece, Turkey, Morocco, France, Bosnia and Herzegovina) (Figure 4).
- **Mediterranean-type climates** defined by Köppen Csa/Csb zones, found also in California, central Chile, southwest Australia, parts of South Africa and Portugal.

Figure 4. Mediterranean basin countries

All studies, regardless of location, were evaluated using the same grading framework based on agroecological conditions (soil, rainfall, topography, and cropping systems) to ensure comparability

Geographic representation is uneven. Spain and Italy dominate the literature, accounting for about **64%** of publications, reflecting their research capacity and implementation experience.

Turkey and Greece contribute moderate coverage, while most other countries appear in one to three studies. No studies were identified for Israel, Palestine, Jordan, Libya, Chile, South Africa, Cyprus, or Malta. Overall, European countries represent 75% of the evidence; North Africa, the Middle East, and the Balkans remain underrepresented (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Distribution of research included in the database

Following this methodology, activities were grouped into seven practice categories. Table 2 lists the practices reviewed and their frequency across the database.

Table 2. Categorization of carbon farming activities in reviewed literature

Carbon Farming group	Activities (Number of occurrences)	Materials / Inputs Used / Technique used
<p>USE OF ORGANIC AMENDMENTS</p>	Biochar (7)	Olive residues
		Pinus pinaster wood chips
		Grape pomace (BC-GP) and rice husks (BC-RH)
		Maize
Biostimulants (4)	CalBio® biostimulant ²	
	Protein hydrolysates + seaweed extracts Trichoderma-based microbial biostimulant inoculation	
Composting (11)	Food waste, green waste (yard trimmings, prunings)	
	Biodegradable kitchen waste	
	Plant-based materials from municipal sources	
	Olive mill wastewater sludge, poultry manure, green waste	
	Solid waste compost and sewage sludge	
Organic fertilization (19)	Organic almond husk fertilization	
	Organic with cattle manure fertilization	
	Organic with green manure fertilization	

² Calbio® is a family of Soluble Powders (SP) formulations based on a synergistic proprietary combination of natural extracts with biostimulant effect under osmotic stress (salt and drought alleviation effect) and other benefits such as prebiotic and germination booster.

organo-mineral fertilization

Cattle, pig, and poultry manure

Oilseed meals as sustainable organic fertilisers

Organic residue (grapevine pruning residue + sheep manure; pruning residue + legume cover crop)

Chipped citrus pruned branches and weeds, and manure from sheep

No-tillage (28)

Direct seeding

Reduce tillage (12)

Occasional tillage, soil conservation

Reduction of land use intensity (3)

Impact of different crops

Erosion protective measures (1)

Erosion barriers

Cover crops and green manure (30)

Native cover crops

Seeded cover crops

Cover crops inter-rows

Permanent natural covers

Passive revegetation

High biomass cover crops

Barley, barley + vetch, barley + vetch + pea

Faba bean

Winter barley and vetch
Inter-row and intra-row - legume mixture, and grass mixture

Silvopastoral (1)

Afforestation (2)

Mulching (10)

Reuse of olive pruning residues
Vineyard pruning residues
Barley straw
Medicago sativa L., Festuca arundinacea (L.), Hordeum vulgare L. Straw and Chopped pine wood Pinus sylvestris L.
Wood chips

Intercropping, alley cropping, living mulch (5)

Capparis spinosa or Thymus hyemalis; barley, vetch, and fava bean
Rye-vetch mixture and spelt
Pigeon bean

Crop rotations (8)

Wheat-chickpea, wheat-faba bean, and wheat-sunflower
Alfalfa and cereals
Wheat with Quinoa (Chenopodium quinoa), or Chickpea (Cicer arietinum)

	Other agronomic management activities (8)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regenerative agriculture Hedgerow Organic farming Conservation agriculture Crop diversification
 CONVERSION TO PERENNIAL CROPS	Land use change (3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Land abandonment Passive revegetation
 SUSTAINABLE WATER MANAGEMENT	Irrigation (2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No irrigation Reduced irrigation

The distribution of CFPs across Mediterranean and related regions reveals both dominant trends and critical gaps. While the use of organic amendments (43 studies), reduced soil disturbance (34), cover crops (29), and agronomic management (16) emerge as the most widely documented practices, other categories remain notably underrepresented. Conversion to perennial crops (3 studies) and sustainable water management (1 study) appear only sporadically, while agroforestry practices are documented solely in EU-based studies. This reflects both the dominance of EU-based research, particularly from Spain and Italy, and a narrower thematic focus in underrepresented regions. Using this structure, the frequency of each CFP type was calculated per region (Figure 6), highlighting dominant practices and geographical gaps.

Figure 6. Distribution of carbon farming practices by region

Notably, research on **low-intervention perennial systems** has demonstrated strong potential for enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC). Schneider et al. (2024) found that revegetation of degraded land in northern Spain increased SOC accumulation, particularly in topsoil layers. Similarly, Lasanta et al. (2020) reported that natural revegetation of abandoned mid-mountain farmland significantly improved soil quality and SOC stocks, underscoring the importance of perennial systems in Mediterranean agroecosystems.

The Balkan region remains underrepresented, with only a few studies addressing CFP and their co-benefits. One of the rare examples, by Županić et al. (2021), discusses **sustainable water management** under climate change scenarios, linking adaptive practices such as improved irrigation scheduling and soil moisture conservation with enhanced climate resilience in Western Balkan agriculture.

Finally, studies from non-EU Mediterranean-type climates, such as the USA and Australia, provide additional insights. In California, Zumkeller et al. (2022) found that the effectiveness of tillage reduction and cover crops on net carbon balance in vineyards depended heavily on site-specific conditions like slope and soil texture. Likewise, Marks et al. (2022) showed that under-vine cover crop management in Australian vineyards influenced SOC input and turnover rates, reinforcing the global relevance of tailored CFPs.

Based on the comprehensive literature review, most studies were published in journals focusing on **soil science, agronomy**, and **environmental sustainability**. This reflects the strong technical and biophysical orientation of carbon farming research.

Out of the 100 articles reviewed, over half appeared in journals specializing in soil quality, nutrient cycling, and land degradation (e.g., *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Geoderma, Soil and Tillage Research, European Journal of Soil Science*). Journals in **sustainability science, environmental systems**, and **plant science** were also represented, though to a lesser extent.

Only a small portion of studies appeared in journals addressing **economic, social**, or **policy** aspects of CF, indicating that co-benefits beyond the environmental domain remain underrepresented in the publication landscape. The thematic distribution of journals is presented in Figure 7, illustrating the dominance of biophysical disciplines and the limited engagement with socio-economic dimensions of carbon farming.

Figure 7. Overview of journals where studies from the database are published (by % of studies published in each category)

It is important to note that the current database reflects documented research outputs, not the full range of practices applied in the field. Many promising CF practices may be implemented in various regions but remain undocumented due to limited research capacity, language barriers, insufficient funding for long-term studies, or because studies of agronomic practices that could be considered *CFPs* were not explicitly reported as such in the title or keywords of the article.

To address this limitation, additional desk research was conducted alongside the systematic literature review. This included the analysis of technical reports, case studies, policy documents, and practitioner-led initiatives to identify relevant practices not well represented in peer-reviewed publications. By incorporating these sources, the report aims to capture both scientifically

validated and practice-based knowledge.

The following chapters analyse the **environmental**, **economic**, and **social dimensions** of CF practices. While grounded in the structured database, the assessment also integrates broader literature to contextualize emerging practices and implementation trends.

4.1.1. Evaluation of Environmental Benefits from Carbon Farming Practices: Insights from the Database

As outlined in the methodology section, all studies included in the database were assessed based on evaluation criteria across three key dimensions: environmental, economic, and social. Each dimension was evaluated separately, using **tailored indicators** to reflect the specific characteristics and objectives relevant to that domain. These criteria will be presented within the respective chapters dedicated to each dimension.

Below (Table 3) is the set of criteria used for evaluating the environmental dimension, focusing on how clearly each study demonstrates ecological co-benefits and their relevance to carbon farming in Mediterranean contexts.

Table 3. Criteria for the database grading

Grade	Very low 1	Low 2	Moderate 3	Strong 4	Outstanding 5
 MAGNITUDE OF IMPACT	Minimal or negligible change	Small-scale or uncertain effects	Moderate improvement in one key parameter	Significant impact with measurable results	Exceptional multi-dimensional impact, clearly quantified
 SIGNIFICANCE	Not relevant in context	Low relevance for the region or system studied	Somewhat relevant, but limited scope	High relevance for the Mediterranean/agricultural context	Crucial for regional/agroecological transformation
 CONTEXTUAL RELEVANCE	Generalized or unclear context	Not well aligned with Mediterranean conditions	Partially relevant or narrow applicability	Well matched to Med/dryland/real-farm settings	Perfect fit for Med systems, scalable and location-specific
 DURATION AND SUSTAINABILITY	One-off or short-term with no follow-up	Limited duration or unclear repeatability	Moderate timeframe (e.g. 1-3 yrs), some applicability	Long-term study or clearly scalable in time	Proven long-term implementation and full sustainability potential
 COMPLETENESS AND REALISM	Fragmented data, experimental only	Simplistic or modelled with missing field validation	Covers key indicators, but lacks breadth or realism	Realistic field results with 2-3 strong dimensions	Highly integrated, realistic, covers multiple indicators clearly

The grading framework described in Table 3 was applied by integrating both the **quantitative outcomes** reported in each study and **expert assessment** of their methodological and contextual robustness. The scoring process relied on systematically organized data in the Excel database, including details such as SOC, SOM, yield changes, biodiversity indicators, study duration, and agroecological context. This structured approach ensured that ratings were not subjective opinions but were based on measurable evidence cross-checked across multiple parameters.

For example, the criterion “Magnitude of Impact” often reflected explicit SOC increases. Studies demonstrating strong multi-dimensional impacts over extended periods received top ratings. This is clearly seen in the large cluster of studies graded 4.5 and 5.0, such as García-Díaz et al. (2018) and Lozano-Garca, B. et al. (2020), which reported substantial gains in SOC, improved aggregate stability, enhanced water retention, and resilience under Mediterranean dryland conditions. These studies combined rigorous field measurements with realistic farm settings, directly aligning with the “Contextual Relevance” and “Completeness and Realism” criteria.

In contrast, the only study receiving a grade below 3 in the database was Schneider et al. (2024), rated 2.5. This lower score was mainly due to its reliance on short-term modelling, limited direct field validation, and broader generalizations that did not fully match Mediterranean-specific agroecological conditions. Its lower marks under “Duration and Sustainability” and “Completeness and Realism” reflected these constraints.

Analysis of the full dataset of 100 studies revealed a **mean grade of 4.24**, with a relatively low **standard deviation of 0.56**, underscoring that most studies consistently achieved high methodological and contextual standards. **Grades ranged from 2.5 to 5.0**, with over 80% of studies falling between 4.0 and 5.0, clearly demonstrating the overall robustness of the evidence base (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Distribution of grades across scientific publications in the database

It is important to underline that the scale was not applied in a purely subjective way. The ratings

were firmly grounded in the quantitative and qualitative data extracted for each study, systematically organized and cross-checked in the Excel database. This included SOC, SOM, yields, biodiversity indices, study duration, and agroecological context. While the evaluation process followed a structured set of predefined criteria, the **complexity and variety of factors** that influence the effectiveness of carbon farming practices such as differences in precipitation, slope, soil type, and cropping systems, often **required expert judgment**. This also considered the quality of the methods used and the overall strength of each study. As a result, the final ratings reflect realistic farming conditions and long-term sustainability.

In carbon farming it is possible to distinguish two types of outcomes:

- **Co-benefits** are intended and direct effects, such as improved soil fertility, crop yields and productivity, water retention, increase of soil organic carbon alongside carbon sequestration.
- **Positive externalities** are indirect, unplanned benefits that often extend beyond the farm, such as enhanced biodiversity, reduced GHG emissions, erosion control, or improved ecosystem health.

The database includes studies that collectively demonstrate a wide range of co-benefits associated with CFP. These co-benefits have been systematically grouped into five thematic categories (Table 4) to better illustrate their multifaceted impacts:

- **Soil biological**,
- **soil chemical**, and
- **soil physical condition**, reflecting functions that influence soil health and productivity;
- **Carbon-specific indicators**, capturing direct contributions to carbon sequestration and reductions in carbon footprints;
- and **Crop yield and plant physiology**, highlighting improvements in both quantity and quality aspects of agricultural production.

Table 4. Identified environmental co-benefits of carbon farming practices documented in the reviewed studies

Soil biological condition	Soil chemical condition	Soil physical condition	Carbon-specific indicators	Crop yield and plant physiology
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in microbial biomass carbon (MBC) 2. Increase in microbial biomass nitrogen (MBN) 3. Increase in microbial respiration 4. Increase in microbial enzyme activities 5. Increase in nitrogen-fixing microbial activity 6. Increase in ammonia-oxidizing microbial activity 7. Increase in soil microbial diversity 8. Increase in denitrification activity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in total nitrogen (TN) 2. Increase in available phosphorus (P2O5) 3. Increase in potassium content (K) 4. Increase in calcium content (Ca) 5. Increase in magnesium content (Mg) 6. Increase in cation exchange capacity 7. Increase in water-soluble carbohydrates 8. Improved overall soil fertility 9. Improved general soil health 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in soil permeability 2. Increase in soil porosity 3. Increase in aggregate stability 4. Increase in soil infiltration rate 5. Increase in water-stable aggregates (WSA) 6. Increase in available water content 7. Increase in soil water/moisture retention 8. Increase in soil water content (SWC) 9. Improved soil structure 10. Improved water use efficiency 11. Reduction in root zone disturbances 12. In-field Soil Erosion Protection 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in soil organic carbon (SOC) 2. Increase in soil organic matter (SOM) 3. Improved SOC distribution (deeper carbon storage) 4. Increase in carbon sequestration rate 5. Increase in carbon input/output balances 6. Increase in total exchangeable carbon (TEC) 7. Reduction in carbon footprint 8. Reduction in hot-water extractable carbon (HWC) 9. Increase in SOC stored by specific crops 10. Increase in carbon contribution from manure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in grain yield 2. Increase in fruit water content 3. Increase in crop growth and biomass 4. Increase in aboveground and belowground dry biomass 5. Increase in dry weight production 6. Increase in total phenolic compounds (polyphenols) 7. Increase in total polyphenol content in oil 8. Increase in sugar content 9. Increase in protein content 10. Increase in oleic acid content in oil 11. Increase in antioxidant and glucosinolate content 12. Increase in anthocyanin levels 13. Increase in 1000 seed weight 14. Increase in cytokinin synthesis 15. Increase in photosynthesis rate and chlorophyll content 16. Increase in plant height 17. Increase in vegetative activity and eco-physiological parameters in leaves 18. Increase in vegetation cover 19. Improved harvest index 20. Improved biomass distribution 21. Improved stomatal conductance 22. Improved relative water content in plants 23. Reduction in oxidative damage 24. Reduction in yield fluctuations

The structured analysis of co-benefits was carried out by systematically extracting all reported co-benefits from each study and then grouping them into five predefined categories, in order to determine which co-benefits were most frequently observed as outcomes of applied carbon farming practices (CFPs) in the reviewed scientific literature:

75 mentions

This is the most reported category in the database, reflecting the core objective of carbon farming: increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) and reducing carbon footprints. Studies report **increases in SOC and SOM levels, deeper SOC distribution, improved sequestration rates, and quantifiable reductions in GHG emissions**. For example, SOC increases are often linked to organic fertilization and cover cropping, particularly in vineyards and olive groves.

56 mentions

This category includes not only yield gains but also improvements in nutritional quality and plant resilience. Common metrics include **fruit water content, biomass growth, and secondary metabolite production** like polyphenols and anthocyanins. Practices such as biochar application, biostimulants, and reduced tillage have shown measurable improvements in **photosynthesis rates, stomatal conductance, and reduced oxidative stress**.

34 mentions

Practices like no-tillage, cover crops, and mulching lead to **better soil structure, increased porosity, higher water retention, and reduced erosion**. The indicators in this category are directly tied to drought resilience and are particularly important in Mediterranean drylands. Reported outcomes include **improved aggregate stability, higher infiltration rates, and available water content**, especially where cover crops or composting were applied.

24 mentions

Improvements in microbial biomass, enzyme activity, and functional diversity are often linked to organic amendments and compost application. These indicators are foundational to long-term fertility and nutrient mineralization. For instance, studies report increased denitrifying activity and nitrogen-fixing bacterial presence after repeated applications of organic matter and reduction of tillage.

21 mentions

Though slightly less represented, this category is crucial for short-term productivity. It includes **increases in total nitrogen, available phosphorus, cation exchange capacity, and overall soil fertility**. Organic fertilisers (e.g., manure, compost) and biostimulants typically drive these improvements.

The co-benefit analysis confirms that, while carbon-specific and productivity-related outcomes dominate research attention, soil health, across physical, chemical, and biological domains, is also frequently represented. This reflects a systematic integration of agronomic and environmental performance metrics in carbon farming assessments.

Cross-analysis of co-benefits by practice group performance (Table 4) reveals consistent associations between specific CFPs and outcome categories. Carbon indicators (SOC and SOM) are the most reported co-benefits, particularly under organic amendments (biochar, compost, organic fertilization), reduced tillage, and cover cropping.

Figure 9 shows the frequency of reported co-benefits across CFP categories in the reviewed studies, highlighting distinct outcome patterns.

Figure 9. Frequency of co-benefit occurrence across carbon farming practice categories in reviewed studies

Although agroforestry, conversion to perennial crops, and sustainable water management appeared less frequently, they still demonstrated targeted benefits, such as contributions to carbon indicators and yield enhancement, pointing to their complementary role in diversified carbon farming strategies. Improvements in **soil physical condition**, including aggregate stability, infiltration, and water retention, are most often linked to reduced disturbance and cover crops,

with additional contributions from organic amendments.

Enhancement of **soil chemical properties**, such as nutrient availability (N, P, K) and cation exchange capacity, is primarily reported under cover crops and organic inputs, with reduced tillage also playing a supporting role.

Soil biological condition benefits, particularly microbial biomass and enzymatic activity, are consistently associated with reduced disturbance, cover cropping, and organic amendments. These indicators are essential for long-term soil function and regenerative capacity.

Improvements in **crop yield and plant physiology**, including biomass gains, improved fruit quality, and stress resilience, are most frequently reported under organic amendments and reduced tillage, followed by cover crops.

Although less frequently cited, **agroforestry, perennial systems**, and **sustainable water management** demonstrate targeted benefits in terms of SOC accumulation and productivity, underscoring their complementary role in diversified carbon farming systems.

Beyond these direct outcomes, a structured classification of positive externalities was also conducted. All indirect, unplanned beneficial impacts reported in the reviewed studies were extracted and categorized into four thematic groups (Table 5). This allows identification of externalities most frequently associated with CFPs and provides insight into the broader environmental and societal value of these practices.

Table 5. Identified the environmental positive externalities of carbon farming practices documented in the reviewed studies

Environmental & resource protection	Climate resilience & adaptation	Biodiversity & ecosystems	Emissions
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction of soil erosion 2. Reduction of sediment and runoff losses 3. Reduction of surface runoff 4. Reduction of soil pollution 5. Reduction of water pollution (stream contamination) 6. Reduction of nitrate leaching and over-fertilization 7. Reduction of soil acidity 8. Reduction of bulk density in soil 9. Reduction of temperature fluctuations in the root zone 10. Reduction of wildfire risks 11. Reduction of nitrogen footprint 12. Reduction of water footprint 13. Reduction of water use overall 14. Reduction in reliance on chemical inputs (herbicides, fertilisers) 15. Air quality improvement 16. Contamination Risk Reduction 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased drought resilience 2. Improved resilience to climate variability 3. Improved flood mitigation capacity 4. General climate adaptation benefits 5. Sustainable water management 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increase in above-ground biodiversity 2. Increase in below-ground biodiversity 3. Creation of more diverse habitats 4. Improvement of landscape structure 5. Increase in phylogenetic diversity 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduction in overall GHG emissions 2. Reduction in CO₂ emissions 3. Reduction in NH₃, N₂O, and NO_x emissions

The structured analysis of positive externalities identified four main categories: **Environmental & Resource Protection**, **Emissions**, **Climate Resilience & Adaptation**, and **Biodiversity & Ecosystems**. These were extracted from reviewed studies and grouped based on reported indirect or unplanned beneficial impacts (Figure 10).

Environmental and resource protection emerged as the most frequent category (60 instances), with reported outcomes including **reduced erosion, lower chemical runoff, improved soil structure, and enhanced resource efficiency**. These effects were most often linked to organic amendments and reduced tillage, followed by cover crops, agroforestry, and agronomic management. Such outcomes are particularly relevant in Mediterranean systems facing soil degradation and water scarcity. The category of **Emissions** was reported 10 times and includes reductions in CO₂, N₂O, NH₃, and NO_x emissions, as well as general greenhouse gas mitigation and decreased carbon footprints. These results demonstrate that several CFPs, particularly those involving reduced tillage, organic amendments, and cover crops, offer measurable contributions to climate mitigation efforts. **Climate resilience and adaptation** (9 instances) was most often associated with reduced tillage, cover crops, and agronomic management, with occasional links to sustainable water management. Reported outcomes included enhanced drought buffering,

reduced flood risk, and greater agroecosystem stability under climate variability. **Biodiversity and ecosystem-related benefits** (8 instances) were primarily associated with agroforestry and selected agronomic practices such as intercropping and hedgerows. These interventions support both above- and below-ground biodiversity and contribute to habitat diversification and ecosystem service provision.

Figure 10 summarizes the distribution of externalities across practice types, showing that soil-focused interventions, particularly organic amendments and reduced disturbance, generate the broadest range of indirect environmental benefits. This supports their relevance in sustainability strategies aimed at Mediterranean agroecosystems.

Figure 10. Frequency of positive externalities occurrence across carbon farming practice categories in reviewed studies

Figure 10 shows that organic amendments, reduced tillage, and cover crops account for the majority of positive externalities, particularly in environmental protection and resource conservation. These practices mitigate erosion, reduce runoff, and enhance soil structure effects, especially relevant in erosion-prone Mediterranean systems. Less frequent but noteworthy contributions were recorded for agroforestry, sustainable water management, and agronomic diversification, underscoring their complementary role. Overall, soil-improving practices deliver the broadest set of externalities, supporting their prioritization in land management strategies under Mediterranean vulnerability contexts.

A quantitative synthesis of peer-reviewed studies identified a set of high-impact carbon farming practices that measurably improve SOC levels in Mediterranean agricultural systems (Table 6). The focus was placed on practices reporting numerical outcomes **in t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹**. The most effective practice was the combination of organic amendments, green manure, and no-tillage, which achieved an average SOC increase of **1.28 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹** (Begum *et al.*, 2022). This integrated strategy enhances biomass input, reduces soil disturbance, and promotes microbial activity critical for carbon stabilization.

Table 6. Summary of Effective Carbon Farming Practices and SOC Outcomes

CFP Type	SOC Change (t C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	Effect Description	Reference(s)
Organic + Green manure + No-tillage	1.28	Highest SOC gain from integrated practices	Begum et al., 2022
Compost (high dose)	1.19	Long-term modelled SOC gain in vegetables	Farina et al., 2018
Intercropping in olive groves	1.10	High root activity and biomass return	Aguilera-Huertas et al., 2024
Organic farming in citrus orchards (long-term)	0.78	SOC doubled over 21 years	Novara et al., 2019
Agroforestry (tree rows)	0.60	SOC doubled in tree rows vs. control	Cardinael et al., 2015
Regenerative woody systems	0.56	Diverse management in orchards	Soto et al., 2022
Biochar application	0.49	SOC doubled, increase in stable C fractions	Nogués et al., 2023; Andrés et al., 2019
Cover crops (barley, vetch)	0.50	Improved SOC and aggregate stability	Repullo-Ruiberriz de Torres et al., 2021
No-tillage (general)	0.47	SOC 33% higher vs. conventional tillage	Franca viglia et al., 2017; Muñoz-Romero et al.
Organic residues in olive groves	0.28	SOM increased from 1.65% to 4.33%; 28% SOM rise	Michalopoulos et al., 2020; Hrameche et al.
Natural revegetation	N/A (absolute gain)	Up to +118 t C ha ⁻¹ and 106% SOC increase	Schneider et al., 2024; Lasanta et al., 2020

The application of high doses of compost also led to significant SOC gains, with up to **1.19 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ sequestered annually** (Farina et al., 2018). Similarly, intercropping in olive groves resulted in SOC increases of **1.10 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹**, particularly in the topsoil layers (Aguilera-Huertas et al., 2024), where root interaction and residue return were maximized.

Other effective practices include:

- Long-term organic farming in citrus orchards: 0.78 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Novara et al., 2019)
- Agroforestry with tree rows: 0.60 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Cardinael et al., 2015)
- Regenerative practices in woody systems: 0.56 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Soto et al., 2022)
- Biochar application: 0.49 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Nogués et al., 2023)
- Use of cover crops (e.g., barley, vetch): 0.50 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Repullo-Ruiberriz de Torres et al., 2021)
- General no-tillage systems: 0.47 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Franca viglia et al., 2017)
- Olive grove residues and organic matter return: 0.28 t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Michalopoulos et al., 2020)

In conclusion, evidence demonstrates that multi-pronged strategies, especially those combining organic amendments, reduced disturbance, permanent soil cover, and diversified rotations, achieve the highest SOC gains. However, outcomes remain sensitive to **local context, duration**

of **intervention**, and **baseline soil conditions**, underscoring the importance of site-specific design in carbon farming programmes. The variability in the outcomes of CFP across the studies is linked to differences in **soil type, precipitation levels, topography (slope), geographical context**, and **crop systems**.

The database includes detailed information on climate, soil, and landscape features for each study site, enabling a deeper analysis of how these factors influence the effectiveness of CFP and which co-benefits are most frequent and most pronounced under certain conditions.

In the following part, all of these factors and their interactions with CFP and associated co-benefits will be presented.

Soil type, particularly its textural characteristics (proportions of clay, sand, and silt), plays an important role in shaping the effectiveness of CFPs and the realization of key co-benefits. Based on a classification of soils into three main texture groups (clay, sandy, and silty soils), the effectiveness and co-benefits of applied CFPs were analyzed (Table 7).

Table 7. Soil texture classes and associated co-benefits from carbon farming practices

Soil Texture	Dominant CFPs	Main Co-benefits	Example Studies
Clay soils	Cover crops, Reduced tillage, Compost/Biochar	Yield, SOC increase, Water retention, Soil structure	Michalopoulos et al. (2020), Repullo-Ruiberriz de Torres et al. (2021), Cardinael et al. (2015)
Sandy soils	Composting, Cover crops, Biochar	Microbial activity, Structure, SOC, Water retention	Nogués et al. (2023), Hrameche et al. (2024), Brunori et al. (2002)
Silty soils	Cover crops, Organic fertilisation, Regeneration	Biodiversity, Microbial biomass, Fertility	Novara et al. (2019), Capó-Bauçà et al. (2019), Schneider et al. (2024)

In addition to SOC and productivity gains, numerous studies reported significant **improvements in physical soil properties** across different texture classes. These include increased infiltration, enhanced porosity, reduced bulk density, and overall better soil structure, key factors in water regulation and resilience. In clay soils, García-Díaz, A. et al. (2018) observed that grass cover in vineyards enhanced soil aggregation and reduced bulk density, while Mazzoncini, M. et al. (2016) reported long-term structural improvements under reduced tillage and organic input systems. In **sandy soils**, Brunori, E. (2020) demonstrated **improved landscape structure and porosity** through agroforestry, and Yılmaz, E. et al. (2019) found increased infiltration and reduced bulk density under cover crop–compost combinations. In **silty soils**, Capó-Bauçà, S. et al. (2017) highlighted **improved infiltration and porosity** under spontaneous green cover, while Almagro, M. et al. (2023) documented enhanced hydraulic conductivity and reduced crusting under conservation practices. A consistent and cross-cutting benefit of CFPs, regardless of soil texture, is the **improvement of biological fertility**. This includes increases in microbial biomass, enzyme activity, and overall soil biological function, key indicators that together form the basis of a

Biological Fertility Index (BFI)³. In **clay soils**, Cirigliano, P. et al. (2023) found that no-till practices substantially **boosted microbial biomass and activity**. Idbella, M. et al. (2024) reported long-term gains in nutrient cycling and microbial health under organic vineyard management, while Jaziri, S. et al. (2022) demonstrated improved enzyme activity and microbial diversity through compost and legumes. In **sandy soils**, Marks, J. N. J. et al. (2022) documented increased microbial biomass and enzyme activity under under-vine cover crops. Andrés, P. et al. (2019) found functional shifts in microbial communities under biochar treatments, and Mekki, A. et al. (2019) quantified significant biomass gains from combined biochar–compost systems. Also, Galán-Martín, Á. et al. (2022) observed increased microbial carbon and enzyme activity in olive groves, and Simona, C. et al. (2024) reported better microbial richness and soil respiration under organic vineyard practices.

Precipitation is a key pedogenetic factor shaping the performance of carbon farming practices (CFPs) and their associated co-benefits. Rainfall regimes influence soil moisture availability, plant growth, microbial activity, and SOC dynamics, while extremes or poor distribution can exacerbate runoff, leaching, and erosion. In Mediterranean and arid environments, aridity strongly conditions the effectiveness of cover crops, organic amendments, and reduced tillage. For this analysis, all study sites were categorized into three precipitation/aridity zones based on reported or approximated annual rainfall, as presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Precipitation levels and associated co-benefits from carbon farming practices

Climate / Precipitation zone	Sum of annual precipitation	Main co-benefits observed	Most effective CFP	Example Studies
Low precipitation (Semi-arid/arid)	< 500 mm	SOC increase, water retention, resilience, reduced erosion	Composting, cover crops, reduced tillage	García-Díaz et al. (2018); Kourgialas et al. (2021); Yılmaz et al. (2019)
Moderate precipitation (semi-humid)	500 – 1000 mm	SOC accumulation, soil fertility, GHG reduction (N ₂ O, NH ₃), BFI improvement	Cover crops, no-tillage, biochar, organic amendments	Mazzoncini et al. (2016); Mekki et al. (2019); Cirigliano et al. (2023)
High precipitation (Humid)	> 1000 mm	SOC gains, reduced runoff, enhanced soil structure, improved physiological traits under excess moisture stress	No-tillage, organic fertilisation, biostimulants	Bombino et al. (2021); Graziani et al. (2022)

For this analysis, study sites were grouped into three precipitation zones (Table 8). **Moderate precipitation areas (500–1000 mm)** were the most represented (47 studies), largely in Mediterranean and temperate systems, showing consistent improvements in SOC, soil structure,

³ The Biological Fertility Index (BFI) is an indicator of soil biological fertility that integrates six parameters: basal respiration (Res_Bas), cumulative respiration (Res_Cum), microbial biomass carbon (Cmicr), soil organic matter (S_O), metabolic quotient (qCO₂), and mineralization quotient (qM). It reflects microbial activity, stress, and organic carbon dynamics in soil (Renzi et al., 2017).

and biological fertility. **Semi-arid/arid zones (<500 mm)** (34 studies) emphasized moisture retention, erosion control, and carbon stabilization as primary benefits. **Humid zones (>1000 mm)** were least represented (7 studies) but reported gains in SOC, nutrient use efficiency, and reduced runoff. Several studies spanned multiple rainfall zones, broadening the evidence base. Overall, CFPs delivered measurable soil and climate benefits across all rainfall regimes, but effectiveness varied with aridity. Semi-arid regions prioritized water retention and resilience, while humid systems emphasized erosion and nutrient management. The most consistent outcomes occurred under moderate rainfall, underscoring the importance of climate-adapted and moisture-sensitive CFP strategies in Mediterranean drylands.

Topography, particularly slope gradient, is a key determinant of runoff, erosion, infiltration, and the stability of soil amendments, thereby shaping the effectiveness of carbon farming practices (CFPs). For this analysis, study sites were grouped into three slope classes: **flat to gentle (0–1%)**, **moderate to steep (1–15%)**, and **steep (>15%)**. Most studies (76) were conducted on moderate to steep slopes (1–15%), reflecting the dominant terrain of Mediterranean agriculture. A smaller subset examined steep slopes (>15%, 9 studies), while flat areas were underrepresented (0–1%, 7 studies).

On flat to gentle slopes, **biochar, organic fertilisation, and no-tillage** were most common. Reported outcomes included SOC gains under biochar (Nogués et al., 2023), long-term increases in rice-based systems (Arshad et al., 2020), and nitrogen improvements after decades of no-tillage (Mazzoncini et al., 2016). Moderate slopes supported the broadest range of practices, including **reduced tillage, intercropping, composting, and biostimulants**. Documented effects included higher nitrogen use efficiency in wheat–faba bean systems (Kaci et al., 2018) and biomass increases from compost and biostimulants (Visconti et al., 2023). On steep slopes, research focused on **erosion control and carbon stabilization**. Cover crops in vineyards reduced GHG emissions under no-till (Marques et al., 2018), passive revegetation increased SOC by 27–54% (Schneider et al., 2024), and natural green cover nearly doubled SOC while improving soil aggregation (Capó-Bauçà et al., 2019).

These findings confirm that slope conditions strongly determine CFP outcomes: flat lands favour SOC accumulation, moderate slopes support diverse practices with agronomic and fertility benefits, and steep slopes prioritize erosion control and carbon retention.

The effectiveness and focus of CFPs vary across **macro-regions**, influenced by **biophysical conditions, policy frameworks**, and the **density of documented research**. Table 9 presents a summary of the most common co-benefits and effective CFPs by macro-region, showing both dominant trends and key knowledge gaps.

Table 9. Region and associated co-benefits from carbon farming practices

Region	Countries Included	Most effective CFP	Main co-benefits observed
EU Mediterranean	Spain, Italy, Greece, Portugal, France, Croatia, Slovenia, Cyprus, Malta	Increased SOC, improved soil structure, erosion control, biodiversity gains	Organic amendments, Cover crops, Reduced tillage, Agroforestry
Balkans	Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Serbia, North Macedonia, Albania	Enhanced climate resilience, better irrigation scheduling, SOC accumulation	Soil moisture management, Organic fertilization
Middle East	Turkey, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Palestine, Jordan	Improved water retention, SOC increase, soil fertility, erosion mitigation	No-till, Cover crops, Composting, Crop diversification
North Africa	Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, Egypt	SOC gains under arid conditions, water retention, climate adaptation	Reduced tillage, No-till, Organic fertilization
Other Mediterranean-type Climates	USA (California), Australia, Chile, South Africa	Carbon sequestration, erosion control, soil structure enhancement	Cover cropping, Reduced tillage, Natural revegetation

While EU countries dominate the scientific literature, the broader Mediterranean and adjacent regions show promising but underreported results. The current dataset reflects research outputs, not actual practice.

Based on FAOSTAT and Eurostat crop statistics (2021–2023), the Mediterranean region is dominated by a combination of staple cereals and high-value perennial crops. The top fifteen crops occupy an estimated **73.75 million hectares**, with wheat alone exceeding **20 million hectares**, accounting for more than 27% of the cultivated area. Olives and barley follow closely, with **11.6 and 10 million hectares**, respectively, reflecting their deep agroecological adaptation and cultural significance in the region.

To contextualize these trends with findings from the scientific literature, the actual area of cultivated crops is compared with their representation in database (Figure 11). This comparison helps identify potential imbalances in research focus. While certain crops, such as grapes and olives, appear consistently across both agricultural and scientific data due to their environmental sensitivity and economic relevance, others, like barley, maize, and sunflower, are notably underrepresented despite their extensive cultivation.

Figure 11. Crop representation in Mediterranean agriculture vs. scientific literature (%)

This comparison highlights significant mismatches. Wheat, the region’s dominant crop with nearly 32% of the cultivated area, is covered in just under 14% of the studies. Conversely, grapevine, which occupies less than 8% of the cultivated area, accounts for nearly 19% of research entries. While olives are proportionally represented in both cultivation and literature, other widespread crops like barley and maize appear less frequently than expected. Almonds and tomatoes are comparatively overrepresented, likely due to their link with specific carbon farming outcomes.

To provide a higher-level view of crop representation, the cultivated species were grouped into broader crop type categories (Table 10). This classification facilitates an overview of how different agricultural systems are represented in the reviewed studies.

Table 10. Grouped crop types with number of species and total occurrences in the analyzed studies

Crop Type	Number of		Plant Species
	species	occurrences	
Cereal	8	30	Barley, Durum Wheat, Maize, Oat, Rice, Wheat
Fruit	7	28	Almond, Citrus, Mandarin, Melon, Olive, Orange, Walnut
Grapevine	1	23	Grapevine
Vegetable	13	21	Broccoli, Cardoon, Cauliflower, Eggplant, Endive, Fennel, Lettuce, Onion, Radish, Sweet Pepper, Tomato, Zucchini
Herb	4	6	Caper, Lavender, Saffron, Thyme
Legume	3	6	Common Bean, Faba Bean, Field Pea
Fodder	3	3	Clover, Grasses, Vetch
Oilseed	2	2	Mustard, Sunflower
Root crop	1	1	Sugar Beet
Forest	1	1	Cork Oak

This overview confirms that the database demonstrates **solid coverage** of the major cultivated crop types in the Mediterranean region, including cereals, fruits, vegetables, and woody perennials. Nevertheless, some important crop groups remain **underrepresented or absent** in the literature, including potatoes, peaches and nectarines, and date palms, despite their widespread cultivation in countries like Egypt, Algeria, and Morocco. Future carbon farming research would benefit from greater inclusion of these crops to ensure more representative insights across different agroecological and cultural production systems.

Beyond representation, the analysis of crop-specific outcomes reveals that the effectiveness and co-benefits of carbon farming practices vary significantly by **crop type**. This variability is linked to both the physiological characteristics of crops and the management practices typically applied within Mediterranean farming systems. Table 11 summarizes the most effective CFPs and the most commonly reported co-benefits for different crop types, with references.

Table 11. Crop type and associated co-benefits from carbon farming practices

Crop type	Most effective CFP	Most documented co-benefits	Example Studies
Olive	No-tillage, Cover crops, Composting, Biochar, Organic fertilization	Microbial activity, nutrient availability, less erosion, better water retention	Michalopoulos et al. (2020), Hrameche et al. (2024), Fernández-Romero et al. (2016), Galán-Martín et al. (2022)
Vineyard	Cover crops, Mulching, Organic fertilization, Biochar	Less erosion, better soil structure, microbial biomass, less runoff	Novara et al. (2019), Raffa et al. (2021), García-Díaz et al. (2018)
Cereal crops	No-tillage, Crop rotation, Organic fertilization	Yield stability, Higher nitrogen use efficiency, better water holding capacity, better mycorrhizae	Francaviglia et al. (2017), Bahri et al. (2019), Tekin et al. (2017)
Almond	Cover crops, Intercropping, No-tillage	Higher N retention, higher plant productivity	Soto et al. (2021), Almagro et al. (2023)
Citrus	Organic fertilization, Cover crops, Regenerative agriculture	Less emissions, better fruit quality, better nutrient cycling	Novara et al. (2019), Cammarata et al. (2025)

Across **Mediterranean cropping systems**, carbon farming practices such as no-tillage, mulching, cover crops, organic amendments, and biochar application have consistently led to significant increases in soil organic carbon (SOC), ranging from **+22%** to over **+100%**, depending on the system. **Olive and vineyard systems** benefit from improved topsoil quality, erosion control, and

microbial activity, while **cereals and almonds** show enhanced nitrogen cycling, microbial biomass, and drought resilience. In **citrus systems**, long-term organic management enhances yield stability and carbon sequestration, with added benefits such as reduced GHG emissions and improved fruit quality.

4.1.2. Enhancing Environmental Sustainability: Positive Externalities of Carbon Farming in the Context of Climate Change

European agriculture faces intensifying climate stress. Rising temperatures, shifting rainfall patterns, extreme weather events, and biodiversity loss are undermining the long-term viability of agrifood systems (Wijerathna-Yapa & Pathirana, 2022). At the same time, farming is a significant source of GHG emissions, making it both a **victim and a driver of climate change** (Murawska & Goryńska-Goldmann, 2023). This dual role creates an urgent need for solutions that simultaneously reduce emissions and strengthen ecosystem resilience.

Globally, agrifood systems contribute about **one-third of anthropogenic GHG** emissions (Crippa et al., 2021; FAO, 2024). This includes methane from livestock and rice cultivation ($\approx 35\%$ of agrifood emissions) and other sources across the value chain. Over half of agrifood-related emissions come directly from on-farm activities (e.g. soil management, livestock, land-use change), with the rest from upstream and downstream processes like fertiliser production, transport, and waste management. At the same time, agriculture is highly vulnerable to climate impacts. Increasing droughts and heatwaves are projected to cause 10–25% crop yield declines by 2050 (IPCC, 2019, 2021), and agrifood systems are expected to bear 26% of economic losses from climate-related disasters – including a striking 83% of all drought-related damage (IPCC, 2021). Recent events underscore these risks: the severe summer 2022 drought in Europe cut maize, sunflower, and soybean yields by 5–10% (Baruth et al., 2022), while extreme floods in 2021 caused €33 billion in damage in Belgium and Germany, including heavy agricultural losses (Fekete & Sandholz, 2021). Overall, the EU has sustained hundreds of billions of euros in damage from extreme weather since 1980, with agriculture among the hardest-hit sectors (EEA, 2022). These trends make it clear that farmers must adapt to conditions far different from the past, posing serious challenges to crop production and land management (Ceglar et al., 2018; Trnka et al., 2011).

All regions of Europe will feel climate change, but impacts vary by region. The Mediterranean is projected to be hit hardest – with sharply higher temperatures, more frequent heatwaves and droughts, and significant biodiversity loss. For example, the number of heatwave days in Southern Europe could increase up to 30-fold compared to 1971–2000 (Devot et al., 2023). These changes threaten water availability and crop yields, raising irrigation demand and risks to livestock. Northern Europe may see some short-term agronomic benefits like longer growing seasons, but will also face increased flooding, soil degradation, and new pest pressures (Midler, 2022). Such divergent trends could intensify production in the north while prompting land abandonment in

the south if farming becomes unprofitable. Moreover, cascading extreme events (e.g. drought followed by heavy rain) can overwhelm agricultural systems – a drought can reduce soil’s ability to absorb water, so subsequent floods inflict greater damage (EEA, 2019). Figure 12 summarizes these climate change risks to agrifood systems, highlighting the sector’s contribution to GHG emissions (~1/3 of the total) alongside its vulnerability to yield declines and supply chain disruptions.

Figure 12. Climate change risks in agrifood systems (FAO & UNDP, 2025)

Figure 13 illustrates how impacts differ across Europe’s biogeographical regions: the **Mediterranean stands out as particularly vulnerable**, whereas northern and western areas face different challenges (EEA, 2019). This regional variability underscores the need for adaptation strategies tailored to local vulnerabilities, especially in southern Europe’s climate-sensitive landscapes.

Figure 13. Main climate impacts on the agriculture sector for the main biogeographical regions in Europe (EEA,2019)

Agriculture's significant footprint also means it holds substantial mitigation potential. Global agri-food GHG emissions rose ~16% from 1990 to 2019, driven mainly by nitrous oxide (N₂O) from soils and methane (CH₄) from livestock (Crippa et al., 2021). As shown in Figure 14, food systems currently account for roughly **31% of global GHG emissions**, with the remaining 69% from non-food sectors (energy, industry, transport, etc.) (Holka et al., 2022).

Figure 14. Share of emissions from the agri-food systems and the non-food sector in global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in 2019. (Holka et al., 2022)

Within agrifood emissions, about **13% of global emissions come from farm-level activities** (soil, livestock, on-site energy), **7% from land-use change** (deforestation, peatland drainage), and **11% from supply chain processes** before and after the farm (inputs production, processing, distribution). This breakdown highlights that agricultural emissions extend beyond the farm gate, reinforcing the need to treat agriculture as a systemic climate actor that spans land management and the broader supply chain.

Despite the challenges, the sector's mitigation potential is immense. The FAO estimates that up to **11.5 Gt CO₂-equivalent** per year could be abated globally in agriculture by 2050 through improved practices (Crippa et al., 2021). This represents a sizable wedge of the reductions needed to meet the Paris Agreement goals. One analysis finds that **farm-level measures alone** (e.g. better soil and livestock management) could deliver nearly **25% of the global emission reductions** required to limit warming to 1.5°C (Roe et al., 2021). In the EU, the agricultural sector has already reduced its emissions by 24% between 1990 and 2021, showing progress is possible (European Commission, 2023). New policies are accelerating this trend – for instance, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) for 2023–2027 places climate action at its core, aligning farm subsidies with the European Green Deal's sustainability goals. Several climate-friendly practices are now encouraged under the CAP. For example, farmers must meet **Good Agricultural and**

Environmental Conditions (GAEC) standards that protect soil and carbon sinks: **GAEC 6** requires minimum soil cover (to prevent erosion and enhance soil carbon), **GAEC 1** preserves permanent grassland (for carbon storage and soil structure), and **GAEC 2** safeguards wetlands and peatlands (major carbon sinks and biodiversity hotspots). The CAP also offers **eco-scheme payments** to reward farmers for voluntary practices that benefit the climate and environment, effectively paying for ecosystem services that markets don't price (European Commission, 2025).

However, agriculture still lags other sectors in climate policy attention. As illustrated in Figure 15, **only 72 climate mitigation policies in the EU explicitly target agriculture**, far fewer than in energy (322 policies), transport (253), or buildings (137) (Van Hoof, 2023). Even broad "economy-wide" measures (132 policies) outnumber those for agriculture.

Figure 15. Number of climate change mitigation policies in the EU for selected sectors (Van Hoof, 2023)

This policy gap is a missed opportunity – the farming sector can deliver multiple co-benefits (enhanced resilience, food security, ecosystem services) alongside mitigation, yet it has not received commensurate focus. Stronger policy frameworks for agriculture are needed to unlock the full benefits of NBS's like carbon farming.

On the international stage, most countries recognize agriculture's role in their climate commitments. About 90% of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) under the Paris Agreement reference agriculture, land use, or forestry (FAO, 2016). These countries account for 92% of global agricultural emissions. Even so, the depth of planned actions varies – nearly all developed countries include farm emissions in mitigation targets, whereas about 30% of developing countries still omit agriculture in their mitigation plans (Wieben, 2019). This indicates

room for greater ambition in agricultural climate action, especially in emerging economies. Considering these gaps, carbon farming is emerging as a targeted, scalable solution to **bridge policy shortfalls, cut GHGs, and enhance climate resilience** on farms.

Scientific estimates reinforce carbon farming's potential scale of impact. One analysis suggests that widespread adoption of regenerative agriculture and conservation tillage worldwide could remove over 70 billion tonnes of CO₂ by 2050 (Marks, 2019). Table 12 summarizes the carbon drawdown potential of key land-management practices from that study.

Table 12. Carbon Draw Down Benefits of Land Management Practices (Marks, 2019)

Practice	CO ₂ Removal Potential by 2050
<i>Regenerative Agriculture</i>	23.15 Billion Tonnes of CO ₂
<i>Managed Grazing</i>	16.34 Billion Tonnes of CO ₂
<i>Conservation Agriculture</i>	17.35 Billion Tonnes of CO ₂
<i>Farmland Restoration</i>	14.08 Billion Tonnes of CO ₂

These figures illustrate that NBS's in agriculture can make a major contribution to climate change mitigation. Notably, many of the practices that sequester carbon (like cover cropping, agroforestry, and restoring degraded land) also strengthen the farm's ability to withstand climate shocks by conserving water and soil— an essential foundation for climate-resilient landscapes.

The evidence is clear: carbon farming offers a **"triple win."** It mitigates climate change, enhances farm resilience, and delivers broader environmental public goods (healthy soils, cleaner water, biodiversity). However, fully realizing this potential requires supportive frameworks. The European Union has begun to take encouraging steps – the recent adoption of the Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation (EU 2024/3012) is one example. This new regulation, published in December 2024, establishes the EU's first **voluntary certification framework for carbon removals and carbon farming practices**. It defines rigorous quality criteria and monitoring requirements for carbon removal projects, aiming to ensure credibility (no "greenwashing") and attract investment into innovative carbon sequestration efforts. The CRCF framework signals high-level recognition of carbon farming's value and should facilitate greater financing and deployment of these practices (EU Climate Action, 2024).

There are various practices of carbon farming which enhances soil carbon sequestration and ultimately contributing to climate change mitigation (Table 13).

Table 13. Carbon sequestration rates of various practices (Priyadarshini et al., 2025)

Carbon Farming Practices	Carbon Sequestration Rates
Cover crops	100–460 kg C/ha/year in the topsoil; 10–320 kg C/ha/year in the subsoil
Crop rotations	Integrating grass-clover: 500 kg/ha C; replacing root crops by cereals: 100 kg C/ha
Grassland management	4 t C/ha/year in the topsoil in temperate grasslands
Agroforestry	1.5 t C/ha/year
Tillage practices	500–1000 kg C/ha/year in croplands

Beyond carbon storage, these practices directly enhance soil fertility, water dynamics, and ecological health, which in turn improves climate resilience. Table 14 highlights the co-benefits of key sustainable practices, such as mixed cropping, cover crops, mulching, and organic fertilisation, on water conservation, erosion control, and biodiversity.

Table 14. Selected sustainable practices and their potential to increase resilience to climate change risks through effects on biodiversity, soil quality and water conservation (Altieri et al, 2015)

Sustainable practices									
Potential effects	Mixed/ Inter-cropping	Agroforestry	Crop rotation	Landscape features	Cover/catch crops	Reduced/ no tillage	Crop residue management	Mulching	Organic fertilisation
Soil Organic Matter (SOM) build up									
Better nutrient cycling									
Soil cover									
Reduced evapotranspiration									
Run-off re- duction									
Increased Water holding capacity									
Better infiltration									
Microclimatic amelioration									
Lower soil compaction									
Lower Soil erosion									
Better hydrological regulation									

Higher water use efficiency									
Stronger mycorrhizal network									

These tables show that carbon farming practices simultaneously contribute to mitigation and adaptation, which strengthens the case for their broader adoption in EU climate and agricultural policy.

4.1.3. Pollinators: Importance and Threats to Ecosystem Resilience

In addition to its climate benefits, carbon farming can yield significant **biodiversity and pollination co-benefits**. Insect pollinators (such as bees, butterflies, and hoverflies) are vital for agricultural productivity and ecosystem health. They transfer pollen between flowers, enabling fruit and seed production in a wide variety of crops and wild plants. Pollinator diversity is especially important: different pollinator species have varied body sizes, feeding habits, and seasonal patterns, so a diverse pollinator community can service a broader range of plants more reliably. This functional diversity makes pollination more efficient and resilient– if one species declines, others can fill its role, ensuring continued crop fertilization and genetic diversity in plants.

In fact, global agriculture’s **dependence on pollinator-dependent crops has grown by over 300% in the past five decades** (Potts et al., 2016). Many high-value crops (fruits, nuts, oilseeds, some vegetables) rely on animal pollination for high yields. However, the degree of dependence varies widely by crop and region. Figure 16 provides a world map of agriculture’s reliance on pollinators, illustrating that some regions and cropping systems are far more vulnerable to pollinator losses than others (Potts et al., 2016). This trend means that as we produce more food, we have also become more intertwined with pollinator services, making pollinator declines a direct threat to global food security.

Figure 16. World map showing agriculture dependence on pollinators (Potts et al., 2016)

Why does pollinator diversity matter? There are several key reasons, each crucial for ecosystem resilience:

- **Reliable, efficient pollination:** Different insects are attracted to different flowers and thrive under different conditions. A diverse pollinator community ensures that a wide array of crops and wild plants get pollinated, even if weather or disease knocks out one pollinator species. This redundancy buffers pollination services against shocks.
- **Plant genetic diversity:** By carrying pollen from various sources, multiple pollinator species foster cross-pollination that produces genetically diverse seeds. Greater genetic variation in plants leads to populations that can better adapt to diseases, pests, and climate shifts.
- **Ecosystem health and food webs:** Pollinators are integral to food chains, they support plant populations that feed other organisms (from insects and birds up to humans). Abundant pollinators lead to more robust plant communities, which in turn sustain soil health, herbivores, predators, and so on. In essence, pollinator diversity underpins broader biodiversity, helping ecosystems withstand and recover from disturbances.

Despite their importance, pollinators are under serious threat worldwide. Major drivers of pollinator decline include:

- **Habitat loss and fragmentation:** Clearing meadows, hedgerows, and forests reduces food and nesting sites, shrinking pollinator populations and foraging ranges (Gatt et al., 2022).
- **Intensive agricultural practices:** Monocultures and chemical inputs degrade soils, remove floral diversity, and expose pollinators to pesticides that harm navigation, reproduction, and survival. Industrial farming's ecosystem simplification is a leading driver of declines.
- **Climate change:** Shifting seasons cause phenological mismatches between flowering and pollinator cycles, while heat and drought stress both plants and insects (Zhao et al., 2022).
- **Diseases and invasive species:** Pathogens like varroa mites in honeybees, or invasive competitors, can devastate native pollinator species, especially when they are already weakened by other stressors.
- **Synergistic effects:** Combined pressures (e.g. habitat loss + pesticide exposure) amplify vulnerability, creating a cycle of decline

The loss of pollinators has profound implications. Reduced pollination can lead to **lower crop yields and quality**, directly affecting farmer **incomes and food availability**. In natural ecosystems, pollinator declines can **disrupt plant regeneration** and lead to cascading effects up the food web. Fewer fruits and seeds mean less food for wildlife, ultimately **diminishing ecosystem services** that humans rely on (Maggi et al., 2024). In

particular, the disappearance of functionally unique pollinators (specialized species that no others can replace) can cause the **collapse of certain plant-pollinator networks**, undermining ecosystem stability.

Recognizing these links, global initiatives have highlighted pollinator conservation as integral to sustainable development. The **IPBES (Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services)** conceptual framework provides a holistic view of how pollinators connect nature and human well-being. Figure 17 illustrates this framework, showing that pollinators and their habitats (part of “Nature”) generate vital nature’s contributions to people (like crop pollination, cultural values, and ecosystem services), which support a good quality of life. It also highlights how various drivers – both direct (e.g. pesticides, climate change) and indirect (e.g. land-use policies, socio-economic factors) affect pollinators and ecosystems. Crucially, the framework underlines that maintaining pollinator populations is not just an ecological issue but also a social and economic one, tied to food security, cultural heritage (think of beekeeping traditions), and livelihoods for farming communities.

Figure 17. IPBES conceptual framework (Potts et al., 2016)

The good news is that many practices that promote carbon sequestration and sustainable agriculture also benefit pollinators. As we “green” agricultural systems, we can simultaneously create environments in which pollinators thrive. A range of strategic responses, from immediate on-farm tweaks to long-term landscape transformations, can

reduce risks to pollinators and enhance their habitats (Potts et al., 2016). Table 15 (from the IPBES assessment) provides an overview of such strategies, spanning different levels of ambition and timescales.

Table 15. Overview of strategic responses to risks and opportunities associated with pollinators and pollination (Potts et al., 2016)

AMBITION	STRATEGY	EXAMPLES OF RESPONSES
TRANSFORMING AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPES	ECOLOGICALLY INTENSIFY AGRICULTURE THROUGH ACTIVE MANAGEMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES	• Support diversified farming systems
		• Promote no-till agriculture
		• Adapt farming to climate change
		• Encourage farmers to work together to plan landscapes; engage communities (participatory management)
		• Promote Integrated Pest Management (IPM)
		• Monitor and evaluate pollination on farms
		• Establish payment for pollination services schemes
		• Develop and build markets for alternative managed pollinators
	STRENGTHEN EXISTING DIVERSIFIED FARMING SYSTEMS	• Support organic farming systems; diversified farming systems; and food security , including the ability to determine one's own agricultural and food policies, resilience and ecological intensification
		• Support "biocultural diversity" conservation approaches through recognition of rights, tenure and strengthening of indigenous and local knowledge and traditional governance that supports pollinators
INVEST IN ECOLOGICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	• Restore natural habitats (also in urban areas)	
	• Protect heritage sites and practices	
	• Increase connectivity between habitat patches	
		• Support large-scale land-use planning and traditional practices that manage habitat patchiness and "biocultural diversity"

In broad terms, the continuum of responses includes:

- **Reducing immediate risks (short-term):** These are relatively straightforward measures to mitigate direct threats to pollinators on farms. Examples include judicious pesticide management (e.g. avoiding spraying during bloom, using integrated pest management to minimize chemical use) and providing artificial nesting sites or flower strips within fields. Such actions can quickly curb pollinator losses and stabilize populations.
- **Strengthening existing diversified systems (medium-term):** This involves supporting and expanding farming systems that are already biodiverse and eco-friendly. For instance, encouraging organic agriculture, mixed cropping, and agroforestry, as well as protecting traditional farming knowledge (e.g. crop rotations, polycultures practiced by indigenous and local communities). These diversified farming approaches inherently support pollinators by offering continuous food sources and habitat, and by avoiding harmful chemicals. Policies under this strategy might include incentives for organic farms or community-led programmes to conserve local crop varieties and wildflower areas.
- **Transforming agricultural landscapes (long-term, high ambition):** This category seeks to redesign agricultural landscapes at scale to integrate ecosystem services. It includes ecological intensification – actively managing ecosystem functions like pollination and natural pest control as part of production. Examples are coordinating land use among farmers to ensure a mosaic of crops and wild habitats, implementing region-wide Integrated Pest Management (IPM) programmes, and setting up mechanisms like payments for pollination services (compensating farmers who maintain bee-friendly habitats). It can also involve developing markets for alternative managed pollinators (e.g. bumblebee or native bee rentals for greenhouse pollination) and rigorously monitoring pollination outcomes on farms to guide adaptive management. This transformative approach often requires collaboration – farmers working together and with other stakeholders to plan landscape-level interventions (e.g. shared flower corridors or habitat reserves).
- **Investing in ecological infrastructure:** A key long-term strategy is to restore and enhance habitats both within and around farms. This means conserving natural areas (field margins, hedgerows, woodlots, wetlands) and improving connectivity between habitat patches so pollinators can move freely across the landscape. Planting hedges, maintaining strips of wildflowers, and leaving some land fallow or “rewilded” are effective tactics. Protecting cultural landscapes (like traditional orchards or terraced fields) that historically support diverse pollinators also falls here. Investing in such ecological infrastructure yields multiple benefits: it bolsters not just pollinators but also soil conservation, water quality, and carbon sequestration – truly a win-win for climate and nature.

In practice, diversifying farmland and adopting agroecological practices are central to helping pollinators. Research shows that farms with a variety of crops and semi-natural features can support much richer pollinator communities than monocultures. For example, intercropping and crop rotation ensure there are blooms available in different seasons, while hedgerows and wildflower buffers provide nectar and nesting sites year-round. Even small actions like leaving strips of uncultivated wildflowers at field edges or planting insectary strips have been proven to increase native pollinator abundance and pollination rates in adjacent crops. These measures often come at low cost and yield tangible paybacks: better pollination can significantly increase fruit set and crop yields, directly benefiting farmers. One notable point is that smallholder farmers (who produce an estimated 50–70% of the world's food) particularly gain from diversified, pollinator-friendly practices (Altieri et al., 2012; Herrero et al., 2010). Enhancing on-farm biodiversity is a pathway to improve resilience and productivity for these farmers, many of whom operate in climate-vulnerable regions.

It's also important to note that local actions become more effective when scaled up to the landscape level. A single farm planting wildflowers will have a greater impact if neighbouring lands also offer habitats, creating a network of resources for pollinators. Thus, community or region-wide initiatives (supported by policy) are crucial – for instance, agri-environment schemes that encourage entire farming communities to reduce pesticide use and maintain flower-rich habitats. By combining within-field diversification (cover crops, polycultures, organic soil management) with landscape diversification (protected natural areas, habitat corridors), we can maximize pollinator recovery (Kremen & Miles, 2012; Wratten et al., 2012). These efforts simultaneously foster other ecosystem services like natural pest control and improved soil and water quality, amplifying their value for climate adaptation.

A pioneering example that operationalizes these concepts is the Azolla Projects Regenerative Carbon Program (2023) – a carbon farming certification methodology that explicitly incorporates biodiversity and pollinator outcomes. Under Azolla's framework, farms do not earn regenerative carbon credits based on carbon sequestration alone; they must also demonstrate measurable co-benefits to receive credits. **Pollinator diversity** is a mandatory indicator, tracked alongside other metrics like soil health, bird biodiversity, water quality, and crop productivity. In other words, a farm practicing carbon sequestration (e.g. through cover cropping or reforestation) will only be certified if it also shows that pollinator populations are improving – tying carbon farming success to ecosystem regeneration.

To implement this, the Azolla Programme uses a hybrid monitoring approach. On the ground, pollinators are surveyed using methods such as transect walks, coloured pan traps, malaise traps (for flying insects), and even passive acoustic monitoring devices that listen for insect activity. These techniques provide robust data on pollinator abundance

and diversity over time. In addition, Azolla evaluates farming practices through checklists and remote sensing – for example, confirming if a farm has planted hedgerows or reduced pesticide usage. The regenerative practices encouraged by Azolla directly benefit pollinators: reducing or eliminating harmful pesticides, planting cover crops and flowering species, maintaining hedgerows and buffer strips, diversifying crop rotations, and setting aside habitat patches are all part of their criteria. Only areas where such pollinator-friendly practices are implemented are eligible for generating Regenerative Carbon Credits. Notably, each project must adopt at least two pollinator-supportive practices from the outset – for instance, switching from synthetic to organic fertilisers, halting the use of bee-toxic chemicals, or introducing rotational grazing to improve floral diversity in pastures.

Azolla's rationale is that **pollinator health is a proxy for overall ecosystem health**. A farm that is truly regenerative will see pollinators return, indicating that the environment is recovering (which often correlates with improved crop yields and soil function). Indeed, Azolla recognizes that **boosting pollinator populations can enhance crop yields and farmer incomes** – a direct economic co-benefit that they factor into the project's value proposition. By quantifying these benefits, the programme aims to issue "high-quality" carbon credits that reflect not just carbon removal but also biodiversity gains and community benefits. This approach aligns well with international recommendations (IPBES, FAO) calling for integrated solutions; it essentially ensures that carbon farming projects also serve as pollinator conservation projects.

The Azolla case exemplifies how carbon farming initiatives can be designed to maximize co-benefits and avoid trade-offs. By setting multi-dimensional targets (carbon + biodiversity + livelihoods) and rigorous monitoring, it provides a model for future programmes. It shows that with thoughtful criteria, carbon markets can incentivize farmers to adopt practices that sequester carbon and restore vital ecosystem services like pollination. Such integrated frameworks could play a key role in scaling up carbon farming while ensuring it truly contributes to a sustainable and climate-resilient agriculture.

4.1.4. Evaluation of Economic Benefits from Carbon Farming Practices: Insights from the Database

Consistent and comprehensive evaluation of the positive economic externalities of carbon farming practices from analysed studies, to enable stakeholders to identify and prioritize practices that deliver the most significant economic benefits, was limited due to limited numbers of papers addressing economic quantifiable indicators on carbon farming benefits. More in detail, nine studies were identified, providing some insights into the economic benefits of carbon farming practices. Summary of main findings, identified practices, economic benefits and opportunities from studies are presented in Table 16.

Table 16. Identified economic co-benefits of carbon farming practices documented in the reviewed studies

Profitability & Yield Stability	Cost Reductions	Carbon Sequestration & Carbon Market Opportunities	Risk Reduction & Long-Term Resilience	Labour & Operational Efficiency Gains	Environmental and Social Incentives
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maintaining or increasing main crop yields 2. Additional income through crop diversification 3. Improved resource use efficiency through occasional tillage in no-till systems 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduced fuel, labour, machinery use, and external inputs through no-tillage, minimum tillage, and organic amendments 2. Lower fertiliser needs and costs via nitrogen-fixing crops and organic amendments 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Potential income from carbon credits and climate incentive programmes through soil carbon sequestration 2. Support for premium pricing and subsidies via carbon-negative systems 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Reduced drought risk, erosion, and vulnerability through improved soil health and water efficiency 2. More stable incomes over time thanks to enhanced system resilience 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Increased operational efficiency and lower costs through reduced labour and machinery time 2. Lower fuel expenses 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Additional income from participation in incentive and payment schemes 2. Lower waste management costs through recycling (e.g., manure)

Given that the database provides limited insights into the economic benefits of carbon farming practices, additional research was conducted to further investigate and quantify these impacts, which are presented in the sections below

4.1.5. Enhancing Economic Sustainability: Positive Externalities of Carbon Farming Practices

Beyond their well-known environmental benefits, carbon farming practices also offer substantial economic advantages. Transitioning to regenerative agriculture can reduce production costs, improve gross margins, and open up access to premium markets through eco-labels and sustainability certifications (e.g. “carbon neutral” or “regenerative organic”). These economic benefits often unfold gradually – the early transition phase may bring yield fluctuations and upfront investment costs – but multiple studies show that the long-term profitability of regenerative farms eventually surpasses conventional systems once a new steady state is reached (Petry et al., 2023; Kurth et al., 2025). The following sections provide an evidence-based overview of the positive economic externalities of carbon farming, focusing on farm productivity, cost savings, profitability, market value, and financial incentives, while omitting environmental and climate aspects.

4.1.5.1. Yield Stability and Productivity Gains

Improving soil health through carbon farming directly contributes to higher and more stable crop yields, which is a key economic benefit for farmers. Healthier soils, richer in organic matter and biodiversity, **enhance nutrient availability and water retention**, thereby boosting productivity. A global meta-analysis by Oldfield et al. (2019) found that increasing soil organic matter can raise average yields by about 5% in maize and 10% in wheat, with even larger gains in degraded soils. Notably, higher soil carbon levels were also associated with a **reduced need for chemical fertilisers**, indicating that building soil organic carbon (SOC) can simultaneously improve output and input efficiency. Long-term field trials corroborate these trends – for example, a study in the United States showed that farming practices which raised SOC from 3.9 to 10.1 g·kg⁻¹ (through cover cropping and rotations) more than **doubled cotton yields over time**. Such improvements underscore how regenerative practices that enrich the soil (e.g. cover crops, compost, reduced tillage) lead to sustainable yield growth once new equilibrium conditions are established.

Table 17. Effect of soil organic carbon (SOC) concentration on yield of cotton (Lal, 2020)

Treatment	SOC content (g kg ⁻¹)	Mean cotton yield (kg ha ⁻¹)1896–1905	Mean cotton yield (kg ha ⁻¹)1986–1995
Continuous cotton			
•No legume cover crop	3.9	896	1,042
• Legume cover crop	7.5	963	2,498
• Fertiliser N*	5.4	—	2,083
2-year rotation			
• Legume cover crop	8.2	974	2,565
• Legume cover crop + Fertiliser N*	10.0	997	2,867
3-year rotation	10.1	829	2,509

Importantly, carbon farming also contributes to **yield stability**, helping farms maintain production under stress conditions. By **increasing soil moisture retention** and **rooting depth**, regenerative methods make crops more resilient to droughts and erratic rainfall. For instance, optimised **irrigation scheduling combined with soil moisture monitoring** can save **20–40% of water with no loss in yield** (Qiao et al., 2019). Similarly, cover cropping has been shown to **reduce soil evaporation and improve water infiltration**, increasing soil water content by an average of ~7% (Basche et al., 2016). As a result, carbon farming systems often **perform better during dry spells** – no-till fields can produce higher yields than conventionally tilled fields in drought years due to improved soil structure and moisture retention. Overall, regenerative practices create a buffer against climatic variability, translating to more consistent outputs and less risk of crop failure. Farmers adopting these practices may observe a **short-term dip in yields immediately after transition** (due to learning curves or reduced inputs), but studies indicate that by **around the third-year yields begin to recover and even improve** as soil fertility regenerates.

4.1.5.2. Input Cost Reduction and Operational Savings

Transitioning to regenerative agriculture is a complex and highly individual process that begins at the farm level, with each farm's journey shaped by its size, land use distribution, crop choices, and livestock types. The shift often requires significant upfront investments in education, planning, and soil testing, which can delay profitability for up to four years compared to conventional systems. To better understand and quantify these dynamics, three representative farm archetypes have been identified- small (50 ha), medium mixed (300 ha), and large crop farms (1,000 ha)- each reflecting common structural characteristics across European agricultural landscapes. Baseline transition scenarios for these archetypes provide valuable insight into the financial and operational challenges farmers may face during the RegenAg adoption period.

However, an important insight from the CFMED project is that in many Mediterranean countries, average farm sizes are much smaller than the "small" 50 ha archetype, often less than 25 ha, with national averages strongly shaped by fragmentation and crop specialisation (e.g., olive groves, vineyards). Indeed, Eurostat data show that almost two-thirds of all EU farms in 2020 were under 5 ha, with particularly high concentrations in Romania, Greece, Portugal, and coastal regions of Spain and Italy (Eurostat, 2022). This structural reality means that Mediterranean farmers may face proportionally higher per-hectare transition costs than farmers in regions dominated by larger holdings such as France, Germany, or Denmark. Addressing this barrier requires organisational solutions, such as farmer cooperatives, producer groups, or other association models, that enable smallholders to pool resources, share knowledge, and collectively absorb the upfront investments needed for regenerative agriculture.

Figure 18. Modelled profit trajectories during the transition from conventional to regenerative agriculture across three representative farm types (Kurth et al., 2025)

The figure illustrates modelled profit trajectories across a small mixed farm (50 ha), a medium mixed farm (300 ha), and a large crop farm (1,000 ha). Each scenario outlines four key phases: preparation, transition, expansion, and steady state, highlighting the typical economic dip during the early years of adoption (especially within the first three years) before profitability gradually recovers and eventually surpasses conventional levels. While these trajectories offer useful insights into potential outcomes, the actual transition process is highly farm-specific. Factors such as the initial soil condition, access to technical support, market integration, and the farmer’s experience can significantly influence both the duration and intensity of this shift. For some, the transition may take longer or come with steeper initial losses, while others may achieve stable gains more quickly.

Although regenerative transition requires upfront investments in planning, training, and equipment (Kurth et al., 2025), one of the **first economic benefits to emerge after the transition begins** is a **reduction in input costs**. Regenerative agriculture techniques are explicitly designed to lower reliance on **expensive inputs like synthetic fertilisers, pesticides, fuel, and irrigation water**. This leads to direct savings in **operational expenses for farmers**. Analyses across Europe show that transitioning to carbon farming can significantly cut input use without sacrificing performance. In a recent benchmarking of 78 regenerative farms in 14 countries (European Alliance for Regenerative Agriculture,

2025), regenerative systems on average matched conventional farms' yields (within a few percent) while achieving a roughly **+20% higher gross margin**. These margin gains were driven by dramatic reductions in inputs – many regenerative farms **reduced synthetic fertiliser and pesticide usage by 50–100%** compared to conventional benchmarks. In Mediterranean regions, for example, some farms achieved near-complete elimination of synthetic inputs: several reported a 100% reduction in chemical nitrogen and phosphorus fertilisers, and others saw a 100% reduction in pesticide use, after adopting practices like legume cover crops and integrated pest management. Such input efficiency not only cuts costs but also shields farmers from price volatility in agro-chemicals and energy.

As demonstrated by Meister et al. (2025), the transition to carbon farming leads to progressive reduction in inputs over 3–5 years.

Figure 19. Regenerative input use reduction over time (Meister et al., 2025)

This trend corresponds with gradual yield recovery, supporting long-term economic resilience for transitioning farms.

Core areas of cost savings through carbon farming include:

- **Fertilisers:** Replacing synthetic fertilisers with organic amendments (compost, manure, nitrogen-fixing cover crops) lowers expenditure on chemical inputs without compromising nutrient supply. Many regenerative farms sharply reduce or even eliminate synthetic NPK fertilisers by maintaining soil fertility naturally.
- **Pesticides:** Enhanced soil health and biodiversity in regenerative systems support natural pest control, while practices like crop rotation and biopesticides reduce the need for costly chemical pesticides. This cuts both material costs and the labour/fuel associated with pesticide application.

- **Water and Irrigation:** Improved soil structure and higher organic matter increase the soil’s water-holding capacity, reducing irrigation requirements. Farms practicing no-till and cover cropping often report using less water, which directly lowers irrigation costs (pumps, energy, water fees) and mitigates drought impact.
- **Fuel and Machinery:** By adopting low-till or no-till methods and optimising field operations, carbon farming curbs fuel consumption and machine wear. Reduced tillage passes, for instance, mean fewer tractor hours and lower diesel use. Over time this translates into savings on fuel, equipment maintenance, and replacements.

These operational savings can accumulate significantly. However, the extent of cost reduction can vary with context – factors like **farm size, soil condition, and the specific mix of practices** influence outcomes. To better understand cost dynamics, Moret-Bailly & Muro (2024) evaluated 49 case studies across the EU, synthesizing the implementation costs, ongoing costs, and benefits of various carbon farming practices. Their analysis confirms that while certain regenerative practices require **moderate to high upfront investments**, most will pay off through input reductions in the medium to long term. Table 17 from their study provides a useful snapshot (selected examples shown below):

Table 18. Overview of Costs, Benefits, and Transition Timeframes for Sustainable Agricultural Practice (Moret-Bailly & Muro, 2024)

Sustainable Practice	Avg. Implementation Cost (EUR/ha) [range]	Avg. Running Cost (EUR/ha/year) [range]	Investment Level	Range of Action	Benefits	Transition Timeframe
Reduced tillage	961 [25–2833]	50 [18–126]	High	New machinery (no-till, direct drilling), higher labour costs, possible initial yield drops	Lower fuel use, less input if combined w/ cover crops, improved soil health → better yields after ~5 years	3 years (5–10 years full benefits; 1–2 if pooled)
Cover crops	x	144 [94–347]	Low	Seeds and inputs, sowing and harvesting	Lower input (fertilisers, pesticides), better yields mid-term	5 years

Organic fertilisation	200 [90–361]	294 [222–365]	Medium	Equipment (e.g. spreader), organic fertilisers, labour, green manure	Lower fertiliser input, improved soil health → better yields mid-term	5–10 years
Diversified crop rotations	300 [200–400]	585 [545–625]	Medium	Labour, equipment, material; seed cost depends on crop	Lower fertiliser use, better mid-term yields (esp. with legumes)	3 to 5–10 years; 3–4 years trial

Across these examples, the pattern is clear: investing in regenerative practices yields dividends through cost savings. Although initial expenditures or slight yield lags can occur, farmers often find that by year 3–5 the reductions in fertiliser, pesticide, fuel, and irrigation expenses begin to outweigh the costs of implementation. In the long run, CF can significantly increase net margins and make farm businesses more economically resilient. In fact, even in regions where regenerative pioneers faced short-term challenges, the overall economic performance has proven positive, indicating strong potential for scalable, cost-efficient regenerative agriculture.

4.1.5.3. Profitability Trajectories and return of investment (ROI)

The combined effect of stable yields and lower inputs is a substantial improvement in farm profitability over time. Several economic modelling studies have demonstrated that regenerative farming can achieve higher profits than conventional farming once the transition period is overcome. For example, Petry et al. (2023) conducted an in-depth analysis of the transition to regenerative practices for wheat farms, modelling two adoption levels (basic vs. advanced regenerative systems). Their results show a **clear profitability trajectory**: farmers can expect a **temporary decline in net profit for the first 3-5 years of transition** (as investments are made and yields may dip), but **thereafter profits recover and surpass conventional farm profits**.

Figure 20. Short-Term Trade-offs and Long-Term Gains in Regenerative Farming (Petry et al., 2023)

In the modelled scenario, a farm implementing a moderate set of regenerative practices ("System 1") achieves about a **+70% increase in profit** at steady state compared to if it had remained conventional, while a farm fully embracing advanced regenerative measures ("System 2") sees **profits grow by up to +120%** versus the conventional baseline. These gains are attributed to improved cropping intensity, sharply reduced input costs, and new revenue streams available to regenerative farms. Crucially, the analysis projects an **ROI of roughly 15-25% in the long run**, confirming that the regenerative transition is not only environmentally sound but also economically viable for producers.

Figure 21. Breakdown of Profit Impacts by Regenerative Farming Interventions (Petry et al., 2023)

The profit superiority of regenerative agriculture is also supported by European case studies. For instance, a recent report noted that regenerative pilot farms in several EU countries managed to increase their gross margins significantly – in some cases by one-third or more – relative to conventional peers. While outcomes can vary (Spain and Portugal initially saw smaller or negative changes, likely due to local constraints), most cases demonstrated that once regenerative systems hit their stride, farm income is higher and more secure than before. Figure 18 (Kurth et al., 2025) illustrates this general trend: after an initial “dip” in the transition phase, regenerative farm profits climb and eventually exceed the profits under conventional farming, across different farm sizes. This transition timeline underlines a key message for stakeholders – **short-term support may be needed to help farmers through the early years, but the long-term payoff is robust.**

It is worth noting that profit trajectories **are farm-specific and depend on factors like initial soil conditions, management skill, and market context.** Nonetheless, the consistent finding is that regenerative agriculture improves the farm’s bottom line over time. In addition to higher yearly profits, regenerative farms also tend to build **more equity (in the form of healthier soils and ecosystems that sustain production with fewer inputs).** This can increase the farm’s **asset value and reduce financial risk.** Overall, CF provides a route to stronger financial performance, turning farms into more profitable and resilient enterprises after the transition period is navigated.

4.1.5.4. Value Creation and Premium Markets

Beyond cost savings and yields, carbon farming can **enhance the market value of agricultural products**. Consumers are showing **growing willingness to support and pay premium prices** for foods produced sustainably, which creates lucrative opportunities for farmers who adopt regenerative practices. By meeting certain standards or certifications, carbon-farmed products can access premium price markets and niche supply chains that reward sustainability. For example, farmers may obtain certifications or labels such as **"Carbon Trust," "Carbon Footprint," "USDA Organic," "EU Organic," "Rainforest Alliance," "Eco-label," and others** which differentiate their products and often allow a price premium over conventional goods (European Alliance for Regenerative Agriculture, 2025; OECD, 2025). These labels tap into a segment of consumers willing to pay more for environmentally responsible products, converting the farm's sustainable practices into added revenue per unit of output.

Table 19. Examples of experiments on eco-labels published between 2007 and 2016 (Yokessa & Marette, 2019)

References	Products	Countries	Methods	Eco-labels	Impact on the market
Van Loo et al. (2014)	Chicken	Belgium	HCE	EU Organic	+
				Belgium Organic	+
				EU AW	+
				CF - 20%	+
				CF - 30%	+
				Free range claim	+
				Nkm	+
Michaud et al. (2013)	Roses	France	RCE	CO ₂ emission	+
				FFFP	+
				Carbon Footprint	+
				Leaf Removal	+
Sörqvist et al. (2013)	Coffee	Sweden	SPLE	STLR	+
				e-f	+
Disdier & Marette (2012)	Shrimp	France	SPLE	EF	+
				Green Label	+
Aprile et al. (2012)	Olive Oil	Italy	HCE	PDO	+
				PGI	+
				Organic Farming	+
Olesen et al. (2010)	Salmon	Norway	RCE	Freedom Food	+
				Organic	+
Tranter et al. (2009)	Carrots	5 EU	CV	CG	+
				Organic	+
	Chicken	5 EU	CV	CG	+
				Organic	+

Bougherara & Combris (2009)	Orange Juice	France	BDM	ATCEP	+
Scarpa et al. (2008)	Carrots	Italy	HCE	Organic	+
				BD	+
				IPM	+
				AWB	+
				Free of Antibiotic	+

NOTES: +: the label positively affects WTP- willingness to pay; N.S.: no significant impact; HCE: Hypothetical choice experiment; RCE: Real choice experiment; SPLE: Stated preference in lab experiment; CV: Contingent valuation; BDM: Becker-DeGroot-Marschak mechanism; USDA: United States Department of Agriculture; EU AW: European Union Animal Welfare; CF-20%: Carbon footprint - 20%; CF- 30%: Carbon footprint - 30%; Nkm: Number of kilometers; FFFP: Fair Flowers Fair Plants; STLR: Shoot Thinning and Leaf Removal; e-f: Eco-friendly; EF: Environmentally friendly; PDO : Protected designation of origin; PGI: Protected geographic indication; 5 EU: Denmark, Ireland, Italy, Portugal, and the United Kingdom; CG: Conversion-grade; ATCEP: Eco-label mentioning that agricultural techniques contribute to environmental protection; BD: Biodynamic production; IPM: Integrated pest management production; EC: Environmentally certified; AWB: Animal well-being.

A comprehensive OECD survey of 37,000 consumers across 40 countries (OECD, 2025) provides insight into this trend. The study found that consumers generally have strong interest in food labels denoting natural or eco-friendly production, and critically, many are ready to pay a higher price for products with sustainability claims. **Willingness to pay (WTP)** for labels like “organic” or “carbon neutral” was especially high among demographics with higher education and income, and in countries with a culture of environmental awareness. **Mediterranean countries**, France, Italy, Spain, Morocco, Egypt, and Turkey, show a generally strong willingness to pay more for food products with sustainability-related claims, particularly those labelled as “**natural**,” “**organic**,” “**eco-friendly**,” and “**local**.”

However, capturing this premium is contingent on trust and verification. The OECD survey also highlighted that consumers’ **trust in sustainability claims varies by country** and is essential to actually realizing higher prices. Therefore, **credible certification and communication are key**. Farmers need to engage with **recognized certification schemes or supply chain programmes** that can authenticate their CF practices. When done properly, the branding and storytelling around carbon farming can enhance a farm’s reputation and access to upscale markets. In practice, this has enabled some producers to enter **export niches or specialty product lines** (such as organic retailers or farm-to-table networks) that yield greater profits per unit sold.

In addition to market premiums, CF creates broader economic, social, and environmental value along the agri-food chain. This is captured in tools such as the **Value Chain Sustainability Heat Map** (FAO and UNIDO, 2024), which assesses value creation across multiple dimensions.

Carbon farming contributes directly to improving multiple high-priority sustainability indicators identified in the heat map. These include:

- **Environmental Sustainability:** CF practices address *highly concerning* issues such as **soil erosion, carbon footprint, air pollution, water pollution**, and **use of synthetic inputs** (fertilisers and pesticides). Through reduced tillage, cover cropping, organic amendments, and biodiversity restoration, CF enhances **soil fertility**, reduces **inorganic and organic waste**, and contributes to **climate mitigation** by increasing carbon sequestration.
- **Economic Sustainability:** Regenerative approaches improve **net income** in the medium to long term by reducing input costs (fertiliser, fuel, water), improving **return on investment**, and enabling access to **consumer surplus** and **price premiums** through certification and sustainable branding. These effects positively impact **direct value added (VA)** and improve farms’ **integration into trade** and sustainable value chains.

- **Social Sustainability:** CF practices indirectly support social dimensions such as **labour rights, food availability**, and **food safety**, especially when implemented in conjunction with local value chains and participatory governance. While not directly targeting all social indicators, CF contributes to **job safety, collective action**, and supports **women's involvement** when paired with inclusive extension services and training.

4.1.5.5. Financial Incentives and Carbon Credits

In addition to market-driven income, there is a growing array of financial incentives designed to reward farmers for the positive externalities of CF. Policymakers, NGOs, and private companies have recognized that regenerative practices generate valuable public goods which are not fully priced by the market. As a result, new funding mechanisms have emerged to compensate farmers for these services and to accelerate the adoption of carbon farming at scale. These mechanisms ensure that pursuing regenerative practices makes **immediate economic sense for farmers**, even before all the long-term cost savings kick in.

Carbon farming incentive schemes can be broadly grouped into three models:

- **Action-based payments:** Farmers are rewarded for adopting defined sustainable practices (e.g., cover cropping, maintaining hedgerows), regardless of measured carbon outcomes. These are simple to administer but do not guarantee emission reductions.
- **Results-based payments:** Rewards are tied to verified climate outcomes (e.g., tonnes of CO₂e sequestered). This provides strong integrity but requires complex and costly monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV).
- **Hybrid models:** Combine elements of both, offering baseline payments for practice adoption with additional rewards for confirmed results. These schemes balance risk reduction for farmers with performance incentives.

These models are delivered through different funding mechanisms:

- Public subsidies and grants (e.g., CAP eco-schemes, LIFE, INTERREG).
- Corporate supply-chain initiatives (“insetting” to reduce scope 3 emissions, e.g., Arla Climate Check).
- Voluntary carbon markets (certified offset credits under standards such as Verra VCS or Gold Standard).

All mechanisms provide additional revenue streams, but high MRV costs can erode profitability, especially for small farms. Current policy and market design efforts focus on streamlining MRV and enabling group certification. EU-funded programmes (LIFE, Horizon Europe, INTERREG) play a central role by supporting innovation, piloting practices, and

shaping enabling frameworks. Carbon farming can be financially attractive if incentives are designed to balance economic viability, environmental integrity, and administrative feasibility.

4.1.6. Evaluation of Social Benefits from Carbon Farming Practices: Insights from the Database

To evaluate the social dimension of carbon farming practices (CFPs), a structured scoring methodology was developed based on international sustainability frameworks and peer-reviewed literature (Table 12). The scale ranges from minimal or no mention of social aspects (score 1) to comprehensive, multi-dimensional analysis supported by validated indicators and stakeholder participation (score 5). Social benefits considered include job creation, food security, rural development, and farmer well-being.

Table 20. Evaluation Scale for Assessing the Presence of Social Externalities in Scientific Papers

Score	Description	Practical Examples
1	Minimal or no mention of social aspects	The paper does not include any relevant themes (e.g., “employment”, “community”)
2	Superficial or passing mention of social benefits, without any explanation or supporting data	E.g., “possible social benefits” with no further elaboration
3	Includes at least one component of social impact (e.g., income, employment)	One aspect is mentioned (e.g., farmer income), but without data or methodology
4	Multiple social impact indicators with quantified results	E.g., workload, labour intensity, perceptions-supported by surveys, analyses, and discussion
5	Comprehensive analysis of social externalities, with validated indicators and multiple sources	Multidimensional, grounded in literature, includes community participation

The scoring design was informed by the FAO SAFA Guidelines (2014), TEEB AgriFood Framework (2018), IPCC AR6 WGII (2022), HLPE Report #15 (2020), and Global assessment of agricultural system redesign for sustainable intensification (2018). These sources emphasize equity, participation, social capital, and community resilience as critical components of sustainability, shaping expectations for higher-scoring studies.

Application of this framework to 100 reviewed articles revealed a major evidence gap. Only **23 studies (23%)** included sufficient information to assess social outcomes, while **77 (77%)** contained no mention of relevant social externalities. Most existing literature therefore neglects issues such as employment, community well-being, and farmer agency, limiting understanding of the broader societal benefits of CFPs.

Figure 23. Distribution of Social Impact Scores Across Relevant Articles

Among the 23 reviewed studies, the mean social impact score **was 2.35** (on a 1–5 scale), with a mode of 2 and a standard deviation of 0.71, indicating clustered and generally low reporting of social co-benefits. **No study achieved the highest rating (score 5)**, and scores ranged from 1 to 4.

Most studies (**52.2%**) **scored 2**, indicating vague mentions of social impacts without evidence. Another **34.8%** **scored 3**, addressing issues like employment but with weak methods. Only one study (**4.3%**) **reached score 4** with some quantification. **8.7%** **scored 1**, offering minimal reference to social aspects. This pattern reveals a systematic gap in the measurement and reporting of social externalities in carbon farming literature. Quantifiable indicators such as **job creation, rural economic resilience, or food security** are rarely integrated. These omissions do not imply that such benefits are absent in practice, but rather that they remain under-documented in scientific analysis.

Despite this limitation, several recurring themes were observed. Reported co-benefits included: **increased employment opportunities in rural areas; improved food security due to yield stability; income gains from reduced input costs; and reduced reliance on synthetic agrochemicals, contributing to lower production costs and potentially lower community exposure.** Some studies also linked carbon farming to **enhanced climate resilience, improved water-use efficiency, and ecosystem services such as biodiversity conservation and soil structure restoration.** A minority referenced **improved crop nutritional quality and human health outcomes.** Additional benefits included **alignment with sustainable agriculture**

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policies and enhanced social cohesion through knowledge exchange among farmers.

Table 21. Classification of Social Outcomes in Carbon Farming Studies

Employment & Workforce	Food Security	Rural Development & Livelihoods	Climate Resilience	Water Savings & Security	Ecosystem Services	Reduced Agrochemical Use	Health & Nutrition	Policy Alignment	Social Cohesion & Community Resilience
17. Creating new jobs 18. Reallocating resources 19. Empowering the rural labour force	6. Increased yield 7. Production stability 8. Better access to food 9. Reduced risk of shortages in local communities	6. Reduction of production costs 7. Increased farmer incomes 8. Economic resilience 9. Retention of rural populations	1. Preservation of soil fertility 2. Yield stability despite droughts 3. Yield stability despite other climate-related challenges	1. Reduction in additional irrigation needs through conservation practices 2. Protection of water resources 3. Increased water availability	1. Improvement of biodiversity 2. Improvement of soil structure 3. Improvement of overall ecosystem health 4. Indirect benefits to communities (e.g., more stable ecosystems, better soil quality)	1. Lower requirements for synthetic fertilisers and pesticides 2. Reduction of community exposure to potentially harmful substances 3. Lowering of farmer input costs	1. Increased levels of bioactive compounds in crops 2. Improved nutritional value of crops 3. Contribution to dietary quality in local populations	1. Support for sustainable agriculture goals (e.g., EU Green Deal) 2. Support for other social initiatives 3. Facilitation of access to incentives and support programmes	1. Strengthening of local networks through collaborative initiatives 2. Enhancement of communities' capacity to adapt to change and crises

Table 13 summarises social co-benefits identified across the reviewed studies. Recurring themes include **employment generation, improved food security, reduced input costs, and enhanced climate resilience**. Fewer studies addressed **water savings, ecosystem services, or indirect health and nutrition impacts**. Table entries also noted **policy alignment and increased social cohesion through knowledge-sharing networks**.

Despite these references, **77% of articles made no mention of social outcomes**, reflecting a systemic gap in the integration of social dimensions into carbon farming research. Notably absent were considerations of social inclusion, particularly regarding women, youth, and marginalised groups. No studies disaggregated data by socio-demographic category or employed participatory methods.

This limited treatment suggests social co-benefits are often viewed as secondary, rather than integral, to sustainable land management. Addressing this gap will require interdisciplinary approaches that integrate agronomic, environmental, and socio-economic metrics and methodologies.

4.1.7. Enhancing Social Sustainability: Positive Externalities of Carbon Farming Practices

Current agri-food systems often overlook critical social dimensions of sustainability. CF goes beyond environmental and economic gains to act as a **catalyst for systemic social change**. By sequestering carbon in soils and transforming farming methods, CF can **empower marginalized producers, improve public health, strengthen community resilience, and foster more equitable food systems**. In short, it generates meaningful social co-benefits and positive externalities alongside its other impacts.

CF-driven change involves all stakeholders in the food system. By addressing key “pressure points” across the value chain – from land and labour conditions to consumer advocacy – food systems can become fairer and more inclusive. Figure 24 illustrates how stakeholders collaborate to promote sustainability and equity at each stage.

Figure 24. Transformational change through strengthening the connections in the value chain, indicating key pressure points (TEEB, 2018)

4.1.7.1. Social Equity and Inclusion

A major social benefit of carbon farming is its potential to promote **equity and inclusion in rural communities** (FAO, 2023; TEEB, 2018; IPES-Food, 2016). Conventional agribusiness models have concentrated power in multinational corporations, often marginalizing small-scale farmers and local stakeholders. In contrast, carbon farming initiatives emphasize participatory approaches that give disadvantaged groups, such as women, indigenous farmers, and youth, greater opportunities and voice in agricultural value chains. Civil society organisations and NGOs have been instrumental in building coalitions (with progressive businesses, labour unions, consumer groups, etc.) to support these inclusive practices and ensure local producers share in the benefits. (TEEB, 2018; IPES-Food, 2016)

Importantly, CF can help level the playing field for smallholders (Lal, 2020; FAO, 2023; HLPE, 2022). Programmes like agro-environmental subsidies or carbon credit schemes often risk favouring larger, well-resourced farms that can more easily access information and meet administrative requirements. Without deliberate safeguards, climate-focused incentives **might inadvertently exacerbate inequalities**, rewarding wealthy landowners while leaving resource-poor farmers behind.

To counter this, experts urge that carbon farming policies include **transitional support, technical assistance, and accessible financing targeted at small and marginalized farmers**. For

example, the FAO and IPCC recommend grants or insurance to help farmers convert to regenerative methods, plus farmer education and local extension services to build capacity. (FAO, 2023; IPCC, 2019; HLPE, 2022) Such measures ensure that the shift to carbon farming is an inclusive transition, so that women, indigenous communities, and family farms can fully participate and benefit. In practice, carbon farming projects that prioritize social justice, by subsidizing small producers, offering training, and involving communities in decision-making, can **actively reduce poverty and inequality** while greening agriculture. The result is not only greater fairness in who gains from sustainable agriculture, but also broader adoption of climate-friendly practices across society. **Equity is thus both a social outcome and a driver of carbon farming's success.**

Figure 25. Illustrative Causal Loop Diagram of a generic eco-agri-food system (TEEB, 2018)

Figure 25 highlights how food production, labour, income, land use, and health outcomes are interlinked, showing that equity and distributional impacts must be considered in transition policies.

4.1.7.2. Community Resilience and Rural Livelihoods

Carbon farming bolsters **community resilience**, helping rural societies withstand environmental and economic shocks. By revitalizing soils and ecosystems, regenerative practices enhance the natural resource base that local communities depend on. For instance, healthier soils with more organic matter retain water and nutrients better, making farms and surrounding areas more resilient to droughts and extreme weather (Rehberger et al., 2023). This translates into more stable crop yields and food supplies even as climate change progresses, which in turn strengthens **food security** for vulnerable populations (IPBES, 2019). Carbon farming also typically diversifies farm outputs (through crop rotations, agroforestry, integrating livestock, etc.), reducing communities' reliance on a single commodity or distant supply chains. This diversity is a buffer against pests, market price swings, and other disruptions. Studies note that agroecological farms practicing carbon sequestration are less dependent on volatile global markets and can **remain stable during crises** such as pandemics or economic downturns (Valencia et al., 2019). In effect, regenerative agriculture creates self-reliant local food systems that are less likely to break down in the face of shocks, thereby safeguarding rural livelihoods and nutrition.

Crucially, carbon farming initiatives contribute to **stronger rural economies and livelihoods**. By emphasizing local value chains (e.g. farmer-to-consumer models, farmers' markets, community-supported agriculture), they allow producers to capture a greater share of food system value (HLPE, 2019). Communities practicing carbon farming often report improved incomes from diversified products (such as high-quality organic produce, agrotourism, or certified carbon credits) and reduced input costs (due to less reliance on expensive chemicals) (FAO, 2019; Ministère de la Transition Écologique, 2022). Engaging in sustainable practices can open new revenue streams. While economic gains are not the primary focus here, they reinforce social benefits by **alleviating rural poverty and discouraging out-migration**. Perhaps even more important are the less tangible aspects: carbon farming tends to build **social capital** in communities. Farmers often organize cooperatives or knowledge-sharing networks to exchange regenerative techniques, and local institutions (like credit groups or seed banks) emerge to support the new practices (FAO, 2019). These community networks enhance trust and cooperation, enabling collective action beyond the farm, from jointly marketing produce to lobbying for supportive policies. In sum, carbon farming helps rural communities become more **resilient, self-reliant, and empowered**, with stronger livelihoods and greater control over their futures.

4.1.7.3. Health and Well-Being

Conventional industrial agriculture has created a vicious cycle of health risks and inequities, which carbon farming can help break. In many regions, chemical-intensive crop production, concentrated livestock operations, ultra-processed diets, and long supply chains all contribute to poor health outcomes (IPES-Food, 2017). These practices introduce multiple impact channels that harm human health, for example, pesticide exposure for farmworkers, environmental contamination of air and water, unsafe or adulterated foods, and the rise of diet-related diseases

from cheap processed foods (FAO, 2019; Lal, 2020). These health burdens fall disproportionately on vulnerable groups like farm labourers, low-income families, and indigenous communities, and they are compounded by social factors such as poverty, inequality, unsanitary living conditions, and climate change (HLPE, 2019; Mbow et al., 2019). In short, under unsustainable farming systems the poorest communities are hit with a double burden: unsafe jobs and unhealthy diets (illustrated on the left and right loops of the figure below).

Figure 26. Understanding health impacts in a food systems context (IPES-Food 2017)

CF represents a **public health intervention** embedded in agriculture. By shifting away from heavy chemical use, it **minimizes exposure to toxins for both farmworkers and consumers**. Practices such as agroforestry, cover cropping, organic composting, and integrated pest management drastically reduce or eliminate synthetic pesticide and fertiliser use. This means fewer cases of pesticide poisoning, respiratory illness, skin conditions, and other occupational health issues among farmers and farm labourers (Feliziani et al., 2025). It also leads to cleaner air and water in farming communities, as runoff of agrochemicals is curtailed (Avasiloaiei et al., 2023). From the consumer standpoint, carbon-farmed produce is generally safer and more nutritious: soils rich in organic matter and microbial life produce crops with lower contamination and higher nutrient content (Ighalo et al., 2025; Bertola et al., 2021). Studies have found, for example, that organically managed soils can yield fruits and vegetables with reduced pesticide residues and improved vitamin and mineral levels. Thus, carbon farming **improves food safety and nutritional quality** at the source, tackling the problem of contaminated or low-quality foods that contribute to poor health.

Another key benefit is enhanced **community health resilience**. Regenerative farming practices bolster ecosystem services, like water filtration, flood control, and climate regulation, that protect public health. By sequestering carbon and rebuilding ecosystems, carbon farming helps **mitigate climate change**, which in turn reduces the incidence of heatwaves, droughts, and pest outbreaks that threaten human health (He et al., 2024; Rattan, 2016). For example, healthier soils can moderate local climate extremes and prevent crop failures, lessening the risk of malnutrition during climate shocks (Valencia et al., 2019). Carbon farming also often comes hand-in-hand with diversified cropping and local food distribution, which improve dietary diversity and food access, reducing hunger and micronutrient deficiencies (HLPE, 2019). Equally important, when implemented with a focus on social justice, carbon farming addresses root causes of health inequity: it can create jobs and raise incomes in rural areas, train marginalized groups in sustainable practices, and build inclusive food networks (FAO, 2019; Mbow et al., 2019). Each of these steps tackles the upstream determinants of health – poverty, inequality, disempowerment – that magnify vulnerabilities. Researchers have thus dubbed carbon farming a “**broadly applicable public health strategy**” because it simultaneously reduces harmful exposures, improves diet and environmental conditions, and strengthens the social fabric of communities (IPES-Food, 2017). Healthier, more resilient populations are the outcome, showcasing how deeply human well-being is tied to how we grow our food.

4.1.7.4. Nutrition and Food Security

Carbon farming contributes to nutrition and food security by reshaping food systems to be **nutrition-sensitive** and centred on people’s needs. Traditional approaches to malnutrition (vitamin supplements, food fortification, biofortified crops, etc.) have treated symptoms in isolation. In contrast, carbon farming embraces a holistic **food systems approach** to nutrition – addressing how food is produced, what kinds of foods are available, and who can access them (TEEB, 2018; HLPE, 2019). By rebuilding healthy soils and ecosystems, carbon farming naturally supports the production of a **diverse range of nutrient-dense foods**. Unlike industrial monocultures that churn out large volumes of a single crop (often requiring later fortification to make up for missing nutrients), regenerative farms cultivate diversity (Wijerathna-Yapa et al., 2022). For example, a carbon farming system might integrate legumes (for protein and nitrogen fixation), fruit and nut trees (for vitamins and healthy fats) in agroforestry, cover crops and vegetables in rotation (for fibre and micronutrients), along with free-range poultry or livestock that cycle nutrients. The result is a farming landscape that yields multiple food groups and nutrients from the same land, effectively creating **nutrient-rich agroecosystems** that align with the dietary needs of the community (Wijerathna-Yapa et al., 2022). Empirical studies have noted higher nutrient densities in crops grown in carbon-rich, biologically active soils, supporting better nutritional outcomes (Ighalo et al., 2025; Singh et al., 2024).

In addition, carbon farming helps **revive local food cultures and shorten the food supply chain**, which has direct nutritional benefits. Locally oriented, sustainable production means fresher produce reaches consumers with minimal transit time, preserving more vitamins and flavour (FAO, 2021). Communities practicing carbon farming often enjoy a greater variety of seasonal foods, as

the focus moves away from standardized commodity crops to diverse native and heritage crops adapted to the local environment (HLPE, 2019). This not only improves dietary diversity but also reinforces cultural food traditions – people become reconnected with where their food comes from and how it is grown, renewing their engagement in cooking and healthy eating. For instance, farmers might reintroduce indigenous grains, beans, or vegetables, providing culturally appropriate nutrition and breaking reliance on ultra-processed foods (HLPE, 2019; FAO, 2021). Such shifts increase **trust in the food system**, as consumers know the producers (or at least the production methods) and gain confidence in food safety and quality. Moreover, by reducing dependence on long, industrial supply chains, carbon farming communities are less exposed to supply disruptions and price volatility. **Food affordability and stability** improve when food is grown nearby: if many small farms around a city produce fresh foods, it can prevent food deserts and keep prices of produce more stable and affordable for low-income consumers (FAO, 2021). There is evidence that regenerative practices (like drought-tolerant agroecology) can stabilize yields during extreme weather, avoiding the price spikes and shortages that typically hurt the poor the most. In this way, carbon farming acts as a **nutritional safety net**, making local food supply more resilient to shocks and ensuring continuous access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food (Singh et al., 2024; FAO, 2021). Advocates note that this approach strengthens the **human right to food**, as sustainable local food systems are better able to deliver year-round, accessible nutrition for all. Future food policies are indeed starting to link regenerative agriculture with public nutrition programmes – for example, some school meal initiatives now prioritize purchasing from local carbon-farming producers, directly connecting soil health to community health.

4.1.7.5. Soil Restoration and Community Well-Being

One of carbon farming's most profound positive externalities is the **restoration of soil health**, which carries cascading social benefits. Soil is not just a medium for crop growth – it underpins a wide array of ecosystem services essential to human well-being and livelihoods. Practices like cover cropping, composting, agroforestry, and reduced tillage rebuild soil organic matter and biodiversity, thereby enhancing these functions (Lal, 2016). Improved soil structure and fertility lead to higher and more stable agricultural productivity, supporting farmers' incomes and local food availability (addressing hunger and poverty goals) (Lal, 2016; Wijerathna-Yapa et al., 2022). But beyond yields, healthy soils provide **clean water** (through filtration and storage in underground aquifers), **climate regulation** (carbon sequestration and moderation of extreme weather), and **biodiversity conservation** (habitat for a quarter of all species) (Lal, 2016). These services have direct social impacts: communities gain access to safer drinking water, protection from floods and droughts, and a more stable climate to secure their homes and crops. In farming regions, better water retention and reduced erosion mean less vulnerability to water scarcity, benefiting both agriculture and households (Singh et al., 2024). By storing carbon and moderating local climates, soils under carbon farming help shield communities from climate extremes and associated disasters (FAO, 2021).

Healthy soil ecosystems also contribute to **public health and cultural well-being** in surprising ways. For example, soil organisms produce biochemical compounds that have been sources of pharmaceuticals (including antibiotics); thus, conserving soil biodiversity can aid medical discoveries (Lal, 2016). Soil is a repository of **cultural and historical knowledge** as well – carbon farming often values soil as an “archive” of climate and human history, and its preservation reinforces **place-based knowledge and intergenerational learning** (Lal, 2016). Many traditional farming communities see regenerative soil practices as reconnecting with ancestral stewardship of the land, which can strengthen cultural identity and community cohesion. In practice, farmers engaged in carbon farming frequently exchange knowledge about soil and ecological indicators, reviving knowledge that may have been lost in industrial farming’s focus on chemicals. The emphasis on soil health thus elevates the social capital of knowledge-sharing and education in rural areas.

Figure 27. Soil health and ecosystem services for human well-being and nature conservancy (Lal, 2016)

Healthy soil functions underpin both human well-being and nature conservation. Carbon farming enhances soil processes – biogeochemical cycles (yellow), water regulation (blue), climate moderation (red), biodiversity support (green), and more – which translate into services like clean water, fertile land, carbon storage, and raw materials. These, in turn, secure livelihoods (left, human well-being) and environmental sustainability (right, nature conservancy).

Investing in soil through carbon farming is truly an investment in **community sustainability**. The multiple co-benefits from soil restoration directly support **social sustainability**: cleaner water means improved public health; fertile soil means better harvests and farmer incomes; carbon sequestration means a safer climate for future generations; and richer biodiversity means opportunities for ecotourism or traditional medicine. Recent assessments have explicitly linked soil health to advancement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) – highlighting, for instance, that regenerative soil management can contribute to **ending poverty (SDG 1)** by

boosting farm income, **zero hunger (SDG 2)** by enhancing food quantity and quality, **good health and well-being (SDG 3)** by producing more nutritious food, **gender equality (SDG 5)** by improving the productivity of women farmers, **clean water (SDG 6)** via improved filtration, and **climate action (SDG 13)** through carbon sequestration. Carbon farming encapsulates these benefits by treating soil not as an inert growing medium, but as a living foundation for sustainable societies. Furthermore, strengthening soil, along with human and physical capital, adds to a nation's **inclusive wealth**, a holistic metric of progress beyond GDP. By restoring natural capital (soils and ecosystems), enhancing human capital (knowledge, nutrition, health), and even building produced capital (e.g. compost facilities, water harvesting infrastructure), carbon farming increases the true wealth of communities. It reduces future social costs (like healthcare and disaster relief) and boosts long-term productivity, thereby aligning short-term farming practices with long-term societal well-being. In this sense, carbon farming is not only an environmental solution but also a **strategic social investment** in resilience, equity, and prosperity for generations to come.

4.1.7.6. Aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

The social externalities of carbon farming map closely to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, underlining its role in a **“safe and just” transition** for both people and planet. A food system grounded in carbon farming supports SDGs across multiple dimensions. In the **People, Dignity, and Justice** domain, it aids in eradicating poverty (SDG 1) and hunger (SDG 2) by improving rural livelihoods and food access, enhances health and well-being (SDG 3) via better nutrition and reduced pollution, promotes gender equality (SDG 5) by empowering women farmers, and helps reduce inequalities (SDG 10) by including marginalized communities. These outcomes show that equitable access to nutritious food, land, and resources – as fostered by carbon farming – is fundamental to a just and inclusive society. In the **Planet** domain, carbon farming obviously advances climate action (SDG 13) through emissions reduction and carbon sequestration and supports life on land (SDG 15) by enhancing biodiversity and soil conservation. It also contributes to clean water (SDG 6) and responsible production (SDG 12) by curbing agrochemical runoff and building sustainable practices. In the **Prosperity** domain, carbon farming fuels inclusive economic growth (SDG 8) and sustainable industry and innovation (SDG 9) by creating green jobs and encouraging agroecological technologies, while also strengthening infrastructure and local value chains that underpin resilient communities. It's increasingly recognized that transforming food systems in this way can drive prosperity without breaching ecological limits.

Figure 28. SDG's three-tiered structure and links to eco-agri-food systems (TEEB, 2018)

Carbon farming reinforces the three interconnected rings of sustainable development in food systems. **The Planet** ring (bottom) includes ecological goals (e.g. climate, water, biodiversity – SDGs 6, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17) that carbon farming supports through soil and ecosystem restoration. The **People, Dignity & Justice** ring (middle) highlights social goals (e.g. no poverty, zero hunger, health, gender equality, reduced inequalities – SDGs 1, 2, 3, 5, 10) advanced by equitable, community-focused food systems. The **Prosperity** ring (top) covers economic goals (e.g. decent work, innovation, infrastructure – SDGs 8, 9, 11) tied to sustainable livelihoods. Carbon farming acts as a lever across all these domains, bridging human well-being and environmental health in the food system.

Notably, projects and policies that link carbon farming with SDG outcomes are gaining traction. Initiatives that explicitly measure and certify contributions to SDGs (like improved nutrition, poverty alleviation, or empowerment of women) tend to attract greater support and funding. In the carbon credit market, for example, credits from projects with verified **social and environmental co-benefits** command a significantly higher price – a recent analysis showed carbon credits with at least one co-benefit certification sold at a **78% price premium** compared to those without. Likewise, credits aligned with multiple SDGs (such as those from community-

centred carbon farming projects) have been trading at about **86% higher prices** than non-SDG-linked offsets. This emerging market preference signals that investors and companies value the broader social impact of climate projects, not just the carbon removal alone. In essence, the positive externalities of carbon farming (jobs, health, food security, etc.) are being recognized as part of the true value of those projects.

Building on this trend, the **Social Cost of Carbon (SCC)** provides an important benchmark for valuing the broader social impacts of mitigation projects. The SCC, currently estimated at about €170 per ton of CO₂ (converted from the U.S. Interagency Working Group's 2023 estimate of \$185/tCO₂; Rennert et al., 2022), represents the full societal damages of emissions – including health care costs, agricultural losses, infrastructure degradation, biodiversity decline, and reduced labour productivity. In contrast, most voluntary carbon credits are still traded between €5 and €15/tCO₂ (Forest Trends' Ecosystem Marketplace, 2023; World Bank, 2024), reflecting only the technical abatement achieved. This stark gap illustrates how social and developmental co-benefits remain largely undervalued. Projects like carbon farming, which generate verified improvements in food security, public health, employment, and social cohesion, directly offset the very damages SCC seeks to quantify. By reducing pesticide exposure, enhancing water quality, or stabilizing local food systems, carbon farming provides value far beyond emission reductions alone. Recognizing these externalities in carbon credit valuation would help reposition such projects closer to their true societal worth, aligning markets with both climate and social justice objectives.

4.2. Pilot Farm Insights: Quantifying Soil Benefits of Carbon Farming

This section presents the analysis of soil sample data collected from three pilot farms located in Catalonia region: Peratallada, Mas La Sala, and Verdcamp Fruits, each representing distinct land management regimes. The assessment aims to evaluate the effects of regenerative versus conventional practices on key soil quality indicators.

Soil samples were analyzed for the following parameters:

- **Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) stock**
- **Bulk density**
- **Total Carbon (TC) content**
- **Total Nitrogen (TN) content**
- **Soil pH**
- **Soil texture**

The results are first presented at the individual farm level, detailing outcomes for each sample and treatment. This is followed by a comparative synthesis of trends observed across all three sites, highlighting consistent patterns and notable variations linked to different management approaches.

4.2.1. Peratallada Farm: Comparison of Conventional and Regenerative Practices

Peratallada is located in the Empordà region characterized by a moderate Mediterranean climate. Based on climatic maps, the area receives approximately **750–800 mm** of annual precipitation, with average temperatures ranging between **16 and 17 °C**. The farm includes plots managed under both **conventional** and **regenerative** practices, as well as a nearby **control site** used for baseline comparisons. Key findings from the soil analysis are summarized in figure below.

Figure 29. Peratallada Farm: Comparison of Conventional and Regenerative Practices

Regenerative farming has not yet shown a large advantage in soil carbon at Peratallada compared to conventional farming, but it also hasn't shown any disadvantage. This effect could be explained due to increased microbial activity and accelerated decomposition of existing organic matter when conventional practices are replaced, leading to short-term carbon loss as CO₂ before SOC levels stabilize and rebuild under regenerative management (Jordon et al.,2022). The regenerative plots do exhibit beneficial signs like lower compaction and active soil processes (pH variability from organic inputs). Given time and continued regenerative practices, the expectation is that these soils will build up more organic matter and display stronger improvements beyond what conventional management can sustain. Thus, **the slightly "worse" showing for regenerative in terms of carbon % is likely temporary or within natural variability**, and not an indicator that regenerative farming is inherently worse – rather, it

underscores the importance of long-term monitoring to capture the full benefits of regenerative agriculture.

4.2.2. Mas La Sala Farm: Comparison of Agroforestry and Pasture Management Practices

Mas La Sala is a high-rainfall, cooler location (precipitation >1200 mm per year, temperature ~10-11 °C). Two land-use treatments are present: **agroforestry** (integration of trees with crops or pasture) and **pasture** (grassland with grazing), along with a **control area**. The higher rainfall and clay-rich soils at this farm likely contribute to greater soil carbon storage potential. Soil textures in Mas La Sala samples are noted as **clay loam** or **sandy clay loam**, indicating generally heavy soils with substantial clay content. Key findings from the soil analysis are summarized in figure below.

Figure 30. Mas La Sala Farm: Comparison of Agroforestry and Pasture Management Practices

Despite high carbon values in all plots, differences in structure and nutrient dynamics reflect the impact of land use. **Agroforestry plots** appear to promote **better soil aggregation** and **slightly higher carbon accumulation**, likely due to root biomass and litter from trees. Pasture soils, while similar in carbon, show signs of **slightly elevated nitrogen**, probably linked to manure inputs or legumes, resulting in lower C:N ratios. The control soil, although clay-rich and naturally carbon-retentive, **lacks organic inputs** and **shows signs of compaction** and **structural degradation**.

Overall, both agroforestry and pasture systems at Mas La Sala demonstrate strong carbon sequestration potential in clay-rich, high-rainfall conditions, with estimated stocks around 70–80 t C/ha. The relatively low bulk density and favourable pH in managed plots point to improved structure and fertility. In contrast, the control soil highlights the limitations of unmanaged clay soils: compaction, lower biological activity, and reduced nutrient cycling. These findings reinforce the role of regenerative land use, particularly agroforestry and managed pasture, in maintaining healthy, carbon-rich soils under Mediterranean mountain conditions.

4.2.3. VerdCamp Fruits Farm: Comparison of Conventional and Regenerative Practices

Verdcamp Fruits is a farm with a drier, warmer climate (precipitation ~550–600 mm, temperature ~19–20 °C). It has plots under conventional management and regenerative practices, plus a control area for comparison. The soils at VerdCamp are generally lighter-textured: most samples are classified as sandy loam or sandy clay loam. Sandy loam indicates a higher proportion of sand, which typically means lower inherent fertility and organic matter, as well as lower water-holding capacity compared to the heavier soils of Mas La Sala. Key findings from the soil analysis are summarized in figure below.

Figure 31. VerdCamp Fruits Farm: Comparison of Conventional and Regenerative Practices

Despite similar carbon levels between treatments, the regenerative plots show clear signs of reduced compaction, slightly enhanced nitrogen levels, and narrower C:N ratios, likely

reflecting the influence of cover cropping, organic inputs, or reduced disturbance. The strong alkalinity observed across all treatments likely reflects the calcareous nature of the parent material or irrigation water, rather than management differences. The control soil, while less compacted than some farmed plots, aligns closely with the same sandy loam classification and shares the overall alkaline character of the site.

Overall, Verdcamp soils do not show major differences in carbon stocks between management systems, but regenerative practices appear to improve structural and nutrient-related indicators: **lower bulk density, slightly higher nitrogen content, and narrower C:N ratios**. These suggest modest **improvements in nutrient cycling** and **soil function** under regenerative management. As with other sites, texture is constant across treatments, indicating that observed differences are primarily due to management rather than soil type. Broader cross-farm comparisons follow in the next section.

Following the within-farm comparisons, the next section will present a cross-farm analysis to highlight broader patterns and differences in soil properties and management effects across the various sites.

4.2.4. Cross-Site Summary

The comparative data across the three farms demonstrate that environmental context, particularly climate and soil texture, is the primary driver of variation in soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks, with management practices influencing secondary indicators such as bulk density, nitrogen content, and C:N ratios.

Figure 32. Comparison of soil indicators under different carbon farming practices across pilot farms

Mas La Sala, with its high rainfall and heavy clay soils, shows the highest SOC values, especially under agroforestry and pasture management. These systems also have the lowest bulk density values, suggesting improved structure and porosity from tree roots and continuous cover. In contrast, Verdcamp, with dry conditions and sandy soils, exhibits the lowest SOC stocks overall, regardless of management approach, though regenerative practices there still resulted in slightly lower compaction and higher nitrogen content compared to conventional.

Peratallada, with intermediate climatic and textural conditions, shows modest differences between conventional and regenerative plots, but regenerative management is associated with slightly improved pH buffering, nitrogen levels, and compaction.

Across all sites, regenerative and agroforestry practices consistently deliver improvements in bulk density and nitrogen availability, though their effects on carbon accumulation remain limited in the short term. This reinforces the understanding that soil structural and fertility benefits emerge

earlier than measurable SOC gains, which require sustained management over longer timescales.

Soil pH trends reflect site-specific conditions: neutral in Mas La Sala, variable in Peratallada, and strongly alkaline in Verdcamp. These findings suggest that pH management must be tailored to local conditions, especially where alkalinity may limit micronutrient availability.

In conclusion, while management plays a clear role in shaping soil health indicators such as structure and nitrogen cycling, the potential for **carbon sequestration is strongly governed by climatic and edaphic constraints**. Regenerative and agroforestry practices show clear promise but must be applied with realistic expectations and adapted to the local context for maximum long-term benefit.

4.3. Field-based assessment of carbon farming positive externalities

The field-based assessment was conducted through the *Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits* (Annex 3), the structure of which is presented in Table 1. The survey targeted farmers implementing regenerative agricultural practices across **six Mediterranean countries**: Greece, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Italy, Spain, and France.

Although the survey was distributed to approximately **120 farms, only 7** fully completed responses were received. This extremely limited sample size poses clear limitations for generalizing findings and prevents any broad or statistically representative conclusions. Instead, the results presented here should be understood as exploratory and illustrative, reflecting the individual experiences and perspectives of a small number of farmers who responded.

Nevertheless, the sample offers valuable qualitative insights from a diversity of socio-professional and geographical contexts, helping to shed light on how carbon farming practices are being interpreted and implemented at the ground level in the Mediterranean region.

An overview of the socio-demographic features of the respondents and the contextual characteristics of their farms is provided in the table below.

Table 22. Socio-Demographic Features and Farm Contexts of the Sample

Demographic Variable	Categories / Values	Frequency (n)
Gender	Male	6
	Female	1
Age (years)	35, 38, 47, 49, 58, 59, 70 (each value = 1 respondent)	7
Educational Level	Secondary education	2
	Vocational training	1
	University degree	4
Country	Spain (Espanya, Catalunya)	4

	Italy	2
	Greece	1
Region / Province	Cádiz, Córdoba, Girona (Spain)	3
	Chieti, Puglia/Brindisi (Italy)	2
	Paros (Greece)	1
	Baix Empordà (Catalonia, Spain)	1
Farm Size	5–20 hectares	4
	20–100 hectares	1
	More than 100 hectares	2
Years Managing the Farm	5, 8, 10, 11, 20, 40 (individual values per respondent)	7

The sample consists of respondents with **diverse socio-demographic and farm-related characteristics**. Participants vary in age, gender, education level, and country of origin, representing different regions across Spain, Italy, and Greece. Their farms also differ in size (from 5 to over 100 hectares) and years of management experience. This heterogeneity reflects a broad range of farming contexts, knowledge levels, and regional conditions relevant to the study.

The survey was designed to explore respondents’ perceptions of the potential social, economic, and environmental benefits associated with the implementation of carbon farming practices. These dimensions were addressed through targeted questions aimed at capturing the broader impacts of such practices within diverse farming contexts. The responses gathered will be presented in the following chapters, allowing for a structured and comprehensive analysis of each category of benefits.

4.3.1. Environmental Benefits Assessment of Carbon Farming Practices Based on Survey Findings

Survey responses provided qualitative evidence of environmental changes associated with carbon farming practices. Four key domains were assessed: **soil quality, biodiversity, water management, and the use of chemical inputs**. Respondents reported perceived improvements in soil organic matter, structure, nutrient retention, and drought resilience. Observations also included increased presence of pollinators, wildlife, and diverse plant species. In terms of water use, respondents noted enhanced retention and reduced irrigation needs. Most also reported reduced reliance on synthetic fertilisers and pesticides.

Figure 13 summarises the number of respondents (N=7) reporting improvements across each environmental category. All respondents noted positive changes in soil quality, biodiversity, and water management. One farmer did not report changes in chemical input use, as they had not previously used such inputs.

Figure 33. Frequency of reported ecological changes following adoption of CFP

Soil quality improvements

Respondents reported multiple improvements in soil-related parameters following the adoption of CFP (Figure 14). All seven noted **increases in soil organic matter, water retention, and reductions in erosion**. Six also observed **enhanced nutrient availability, improved soil structure, higher yields, and better resilience** to drought and extreme weather.

Figure 34. Reported improvements in soil quality following adoption of CFP

Beyond these core improvements, some respondents also noted **additional positive effects**, such as accelerated growth and a greater presence of beneficial insects and fauna. These findings suggest that carbon farming contributes to both ecological and agricultural outcomes, reinforcing its potential for long-term effectiveness and integration into sustainable land management practices.

Use of chemical fertilisers and pesticides

Respondents reported a marked reduction in the use of chemical fertilisers following the adoption of carbon farming practices (Figure 15). Two discontinued synthetic inputs entirely, opting for livestock-based fertilisation. Others reported reductions of 70%, 50%, or 25%. One respondent noted that chemical fertilisers had never been used, indicating a pre-existing low-input approach.

Figure 35. Reported Changes in the use of chemical fertilisers following adaptation of CFP

Pesticide use followed a similar trend (Figure 16). Four respondents reported never using pesticides, while two reported complete discontinuation and one cited a 30% reduction.

Figure 36. Reported changes in the use of pesticides following adaptation of CFP

Biodiversity changes

The transition to carbon farming practices has contributed to **enhanced biodiversity** on agricultural land. Respondents reported perceived improvements in on-farm biodiversity following the adoption of carbon farming practices. All seven noted increases in pollinators, beneficial insects, and bird populations. Six also observed greater plant diversity and more frequent presence of wildlife. These observations suggest that regenerative practices may support key functional groups within the agroecosystem. Reported changes are summarised in Figure 17.

Figure 37. Reported improvements in biodiversity following adaptation of CFP

Water management adaptations

Respondents reported several water-related changes following the adoption of carbon farming practices. Most noted improved soil water retention, while others reported reduced irrigation needs, greater drought resilience, and improved drainage Figure 18. One respondent also described transitioning to a fully rainfed system.

Figure 38. Reported Water Management Adaptations Following the Adoption of Carbon Farming Practices

These observations suggest that regenerative practices may enhance water-use efficiency and adaptive capacity in farm systems exposed to irregular rainfall and drought, an especially relevant consideration in Mediterranean agro-ecosystems.

4.3.2. Economic Benefits Assessment of Carbon Farming Practices on Pilot Farms

This section presents farmer-reported economic outcomes following the adoption of carbon farming practices. Four dimensions were assessed: changes in crop yields, operational cost savings, participation in carbon credit mechanisms, and access to new markets.

Crop Yields

Most respondents (6 of 7) reported yield increases after implementing carbon farming practices (Figure 19). Reported gains ranged from 10% to 30%, with one respondent noting variability depending on rainfall. No declines were reported. These trends suggest a potential for maintaining or improving productivity under regenerative management.

Figure 39. Percentage Increase in Crop Yields Reported by Farmers Following the Adoption of Carbon Farming Practices

Cost Savings

Five respondents noted reductions in operational costs (Figure 20), primarily due to lower use of fuel, fertilisers, pesticides, and water. Isolated savings were also noted in pest treatments and subcontracted work.

Figure 40. Reported Cost Savings in Agricultural Operations After Implementing Carbon Farming

Carbon Credits

Three respondents reported participating in carbon credit programmes, while four were not involved. This indicates limited but emerging engagement with ecosystem service markets.

Market Access

Four respondents noted improved market access, citing opportunities to enter high-value segments, improved product image, and greater willingness among clients to pay for sustainable practices. These observations suggest that carbon farming may offer marketing co-benefits under

4.3.3.Social Benefits Assessment of Carbon Farming Practices on Pilot Farms

The survey included a dedicated section focused on exploring the **social co-benefits** of implementing carbon farming practices. It aimed to capture farmers’ perceptions of how these practices influence **labour dynamics, community interactions,** and **overall quality of life.**

Labour Requirements & Workforce Dynamics

Five respondents reported increased labour needs following adoption of carbon farming practices (Figure 21). However, only two hired additional workers, indicating that increased workloads were often managed within existing family or staff structures. One respondent reported a decrease in labour needs, and one saw no change.

Figure 41. Changes in Labour Demand Following Carbon Farming Implementation

Local Community Impact

Respondents reported several perceived benefits of carbon farming at the community level (Figure 22). All indicated a positive impact, most frequently citing **knowledge sharing, collaboration with other farmers, and improved local food security**. Three respondents also associated carbon farming with job creation. Isolated references were made to learning from neighbours and collaboration with agronomic centres. These responses suggest that carbon farming may foster local exchange networks and support community-level resilience, especially relevant in regions facing rural depopulation and declining inter-farm cooperation.

Figure 42. Community-Level Benefits Reported by Surveyed Farmers

Perceived Quality of Life Improvements

Respondents reported a range of perceived improvements in quality of life associated with the adoption of carbon farming practices (Figure 23). Key themes included **better work-life balance, reduced exposure to chemicals**, and a **stronger sense of satisfaction** with sustainable agriculture. Other responses included references to future land stewardship and landscape aesthetics.

Figure 43. Reported Quality of Life and Wellbeing Indicators Among Respondents

These findings suggest that carbon farming may contribute to subjective well-being for some farmers, particularly through reduced chemical exposure and lifestyle balance. However, the results are based on self-reported perceptions from a small sample and should be interpreted accordingly.

Overall, respondents identified positive changes across labour patterns, community engagement, and personal well-being. Reported co-benefits included increased collaboration, informal knowledge exchange, and a stronger connection to sustainable land stewardship. While these results are not representative, they underscore the need for further research into the social impacts of carbon farming using larger and more diverse samples.

5. Conclusions

The evidence compiled in this report demonstrates that carbon farming practices deliver a wide spectrum of **positive externalities** across economic, social, and environmental dimensions, with substantial implications for sustainable agriculture and climate change mitigation in **Mediterranean contexts**.

From an **economic** perspective, regenerative approaches such as organic amendments, reduced tillage, and cover cropping have been consistently linked with enhanced profitability through yield stability, improved product quality, reduced input costs, and access to premium markets (*Kurth et al., 2025; Meister et al., 2025; Moret-Bailly & Muro, 2024*). The integration of practices like composting and no-tillage has shown the highest soil organic carbon (SOC) gains (*Begum et al., 2022; Farina et al., 2018*), which in turn can enhance the long-term financial viability of farms and increase the value of associated carbon credits.

Social benefits include strengthened rural livelihoods, employment creation, intergenerational knowledge transfer, and greater community resilience to socio-economic and climatic stressors (*Rouabhi et al, 2019; González-Rosado et al., 2023*). Many farmers reported improved food security and quality of life as a result of diversified and resilient production systems.

Environmental benefits are particularly well-documented. Carbon farming practices have contributed to measurable improvements in soil health (biological, chemical, and physical), increased water retention, reduced erosion, and enhanced biodiversity (*García-Díaz et al., 2018; Cardinael et al., 2015*). Climate resilience benefits, such as drought tolerance and flood mitigation, have been observed across varying precipitation zones, while emission reductions (CO₂, N₂O, NH₃) further enhance the climate mitigation potential (*Marques et al., 2018; Mekki et al., 2019*).

To provide a clear and consolidated overview, **the table below summarises the key benefits across all three dimensions**, economic, environmental, and social, highlighting their interconnected role in delivering holistic sustainability outcome.

Table 23. Summary of key benefits of carbon farming practices

CO-BENEFIT CATEGORY		EXPLANATION / MECHANISM	MEASUREMENT INDICATOR	POTENTIAL IMPACT ON CARBON CREDIT PREMIUM
ENVIRONMENTAL CO-BENEFITS				
IMPROVED HEALTH	SOIL	Carbon farming practices such as cover cropping, reduced tillage, and organic fertilisation increase soil organic matter, enhance nutrient cycling, and improve soil structure.	Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) content, nutrient availability tests, soil structure assessments.	HIGH – healthier soils increase permanence and credibility of carbon sequestration, making credits more attractive to buyers.
ENHANCED BIODIVERSITY		Agroforestry, habitat restoration, and diversified cropping systems create habitats for flora and fauna, supporting ecosystem services.	Species richness and abundance surveys, pollinator counts, biodiversity indices.	HIGH – biodiversity co-benefits are highly valued in premium voluntary carbon markets.
IMPROVED RETENTION	WATER	Practices such as mulching, cover crops, and organic amendments increase soil water-holding capacity, reducing drought stress.	Soil moisture content, infiltration rates, crop yield stability during dry periods.	MODERATE- HIGH – enhances climate resilience, appealing to adaptation-focused buyers.
REDUCED EROSION	SOIL	Permanent ground cover and contour farming reduce topsoil loss, protecting long-term productivity.	Soil erosion rate measurements, sediment load in waterways.	MODERATE – links carbon sequestration with land degradation neutrality targets.
PROTECTION OF WETLANDS AND PEATLANDS AS CARBON SINKS	OF AND AS	Avoided drainage and restoration of wetlands and peatlands preserve large carbon stocks and provide biodiversity and water regulation benefits.	Area of wetlands/peatlands protected, GHG flux measurements from restored sites.	HIGH – large carbon storage potential and strong co-benefits increase premium value.
RESTORATION OF DEGRADED LAND	OF	Revegetation, organic amendments, and erosion control rehabilitate degraded soils, improving carbon storage and	Vegetation cover change, SOC increase, land productivity indices.	HIGH – demonstrates additionality and long-term sustainability.

	productivity.		
ENHANCED RESILIENCE TO EXTREME WEATHER	Diversified cropping, agroforestry, and improved soil health buffer farms against floods, droughts, and heatwaves.	Yield stability across years, damage reports after extreme events.	MODERATE- HIGH – climate adaptation benefits are increasingly demanded by investors.
ECONOMIC CO-BENEFITS			
REDUCTION IN INPUT COSTS	Adoption of practices such as cover cropping, organic fertilization, and integrated pest management leads to decreased reliance on synthetic inputs.	Percentage reduction in expenditures on fertilisers, pesticides, irrigation, and fuel.	MODERATE- HIGH: Enhances cost-efficiency and return per unit area.
IMPROVED YIELD STABILITY	Enhanced soil structure, organic matter, and water retention reduce crop vulnerability to climate variability and extreme weather.	Inter-annual yield variability; yield loss frequency under climate stress.	MODERATE: Supports income predictability, which improves investment attractiveness.
INCREASED MARKET VALUE OF PRODUCE	Higher quality and differentiated products (e.g., organic, high nutrient density) command price premiums and access to value-added markets.	Price differential between conventional and sustainably grown produce; market share in premium segments.	HIGH: Facilitates higher net revenues and strengthens the business case for CF.
ENHANCED FARM PROFITABILITY	Combined effect of cost reduction, stable yields, and better pricing leads to improved net profit margins and return on investment (ROI).	Profit per hectare; ROI over a multi-year period; gross margin comparisons.	HIGH: Demonstrates the financial sustainability of carbon farming systems.
ACCESS TO SUBSIDIES AND INCENTIVES	Carbon farming practices can unlock participation in agri-environmental schemes, climate funds, or carbon markets through improved eligibility.	Share of income from public or private incentives; enrolment in carbon crediting mechanisms.	MODERATE: Adds financial leverage, particularly for smallholder participation.

<p>INCOME DIVERSIFICATION</p>	<p>Integration of agroforestry, carbon credit trading, or eco-tourism enhances resilience by reducing dependency on single revenue streams.</p>	<p>Number of distinct income sources; proportion of income from non-traditional sources (e.g. carbon sales).</p>	<p>MODERATE-HIGH: Increases adaptive capacity and financial robustness.</p>
<p>SOCIAL CO-BENEFITS</p>			
<p>LOCAL EMPLOYMENT & RURAL JOBS</p>	<p>Increases on-farm labour needs (e.g. for cover cropping, composting), potentially creating new farm jobs and service roles Supports rural economies by retaining or attracting workers (e.g. youth staying in agriculture)</p>	<p>% change in labour demand Number of FTEs created Demographic disaggregation (e.g. youth, women)</p>	<p>MODERATE - HIGH: Documented job creation appeals to buyers' CSR goals (SDGs 1 & 8). Projects with clear local employment benefits can command premium prices, as buyers value community uplift. Co-benefit certifications that include economic development often see significantly higher prices (credits with co-benefits average ~78% price).</p>
<p>FARMER LIVELIHOODS (INCOME & COST SAVINGS)</p>	<p>Lowers input costs (less synthetic fertiliser/pesticide use) and diversifies farm products, improving net income Enhances yield stability, reducing income volatility from climate or market shocks Carbon credit revenue itself provides a supplementary income stream</p>	<p>Change in gross margins Change in net margins Net farm income Income per household (before and after intervention) Income stability (seasonal or annual variance) Income diversification ratio (number and type of income streams) Living income benchmark / gap (e.g. Anker methodology) Household income relative</p>	<p>HIGH: Improved livelihoods (aligning with SDGs 1 & 2) make credits attractive to impact investors. Buyers often pay more for credits that alleviate poverty or boost farmer incomes. Projects that can show poverty reduction or increased profitability for farmers are likely to fetch upper-range prices. (Many carbon standards reward such co-benefits with tags/labels, supporting premium pricing.)</p>

		to poverty threshold Cost-efficiency ratio (e.g. input cost per hectare or per kg yield) Income resilience under climate or market shocks	
FOOD SECURITY & NUTRITION	Increases or stabilizes crop yields and food production, improving local food availability and affordability Enhances nutritional quality of produce (e.g. higher micronutrients or less chemical residues in crops) Diversifies food sources (agroforestry, intercropping) for more balanced diets and year-round supply	% change in food availability Crop nutritional quality indices Household Dietary Diversity Score	HIGH: Credits from projects that bolster food security (SDG 2) and community nutrition are viewed favourably. Companies and consumers may pay a premium for offsets that also fight hunger or improve nutrition. Proven yield gains and resilience can elevate a project's story, often leading to higher willingness-to-pay among buyers focused on sustainable development co-benefits (credits linked to SDG2 often garner above-average prices)
COMMUNITY COHESION & KNOWLEDGE SHARING	Fosters social networks as farmers collaborate on new practices (e.g. co-ops for composting, farmer field schools) Promotes knowledge exchange and co-learning (farmers teaching peers, sharing traditional knowledge and innovations) Strengthens community organisations and trust, building social capital that can help in other collective initiatives	Number of peer groups/meetings Participation in field schools Joint resource use initiatives	MODERATE: While harder to quantify, strong community engagement adds narrative value to credits. Projects that unite communities and facilitate education tend to meet corporate social responsibility criteria, making the credits more marketable. Buyers seeking community impact (SDGs 4 & 11) may pay a premium for these projects, although the impact is usually realized through storytelling and certification endorsements rather than a fixed price increase.
HEALTH & WELL-BEING (PUBLIC)	Reduces exposure to harmful agrochemicals for farmers and locals	Reported health incidents Agrochemical usage levels	HIGH: Health co-benefits are highly valued in the carbon market. Projects that demonstrably improve

<p>HEALTH)</p>	<p>(less pesticide use means lower health risks and cleaner water) Improves dietary health by providing chemical-free, nutrient-rich foods and encouraging diversified diets Enhances overall well-being and work conditions (farmers report better work-life balance and satisfaction under sustainable practices)</p>	<p>% of chemical-free production</p>	<p>community health (clean water, less pollution, better nutrition – contributing to SDG 3) often secure premium pricing. Buyers are willing to pay more for credits that also deliver tangible health outcomes. In some cases, the added health and social value per credit can far exceed the carbon value, indicating strong justification for a higher price.</p>
<p>CLIMATE RESILIENCE FOR COMMUNITIES</p>	<p>Builds resilience against climate impacts by improving soil moisture, biodiversity, and farm ecosystem health (e.g. farms better withstand droughts or floods) Stabilizes yields and incomes year-to-year despite weather extremes, which protects communities from climate-induced food shortages or economic shocks Strengthens adaptive capacity through diversification (mixing crops/livestock spreads risk)</p>	<p>Yield variance under extreme weather % of land with resilient practices Water retention capacity of soil</p>	<p>MODERATE: Credits from adaptation-friendly projects appeal to buyers interested in climate resilience (an emerging priority). While carbon markets primarily value emissions, showing added resilience benefit can attract a subset of buyers (including climate adaptation funds or insurers) and justify a premium. For instance, a project that prevents climate-related crop failures provides stability that some buyers will reward, though this co-benefit often complements the sales pitch rather than dramatically increasing price by itself.</p>
<p>SOCIAL INCLUSION & GENDER EQUITY</p>	<p>Empowers women, youth, and marginalized groups by design: carbon farming projects can involve women in training, leadership roles, or income activities (e.g. agro-processing), and encourage youth to engage in innovative farming rather than migrate</p>	<p>%of female/youth beneficiaries Gender-disaggregated income data</p>	<p>HIGH (if achieved): Inclusivity boosts a project’s profile significantly. Carbon credits that can be tied to women’s empowerment or poverty reduction among marginalized groups tap into a strong demand niche (aligning with SDGs 5 & 10). Many buyers (and standards like Gold Standard Gender tag) will favour and pay extra for credits</p>

	Fair benefit-sharing: Ensures smallholders and vulnerable groups gain from carbon revenues and capacity-building, improving equity and community cohesion		demonstrating social equity. However, such outcomes must be credibly measured; when they are, they can place the credit in a top premium bracket due to the strong narrative and ethical appeal.
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Taken together, these externalities reinforce the **overall importance** of carbon farming as a tool for achieving integrated sustainability objectives. Beyond carbon sequestration, the combined economic, environmental, and social co-benefits align closely with EU Green Deal targets, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and Mediterranean strategies for climate adaptation and rural development. Recognizing and integrating these externalities into carbon credit valuation frameworks can significantly increase the credibility, attractiveness, and market differentiation of such credits, particularly for ESG-oriented investors and sustainable supply chains.

However, **challenges remain** in fully capturing and maximizing these benefits. Economic and especially social co-benefits are underrepresented in existing literature, with measurement hindered by the lack of standardized indicators and limited longitudinal data. Variability in outcomes due to site-specific factors, such as soil type, topography, and precipitation, underscores the need for tailored, context-sensitive approaches.

Future research should prioritize filling these knowledge gaps through long-term, region-specific studies, especially in underrepresented Mediterranean subregions. Methodological innovations are needed to **standardize measurement of co-benefits**, enabling their integration into carbon credit certification schemes. Policies should incentivize practices that deliver high-value co-benefits, and market mechanisms should reflect the added worth of credits tied to ecosystem services, biodiversity gains, and rural socio-economic resilience.

In conclusion, carbon farming represents a **high-potential, multi-benefit pathway** for sustainable agriculture in the Mediterranean. By embedding its positive externalities into the core of carbon credit valuation, stakeholders can ensure that these systems gain wider adoption, unlock greater market opportunities, and deliver long-term climate and development benefits.

6. Annexes

Annex 1- List of Publications Included in the Database

1. Acar, M., Çelik, İ., & Günal, H. (2017). Effects of long-term tillage systems on soil water content and wheat yield under Mediterranean conditions. *Journal of New theory*, (17), 98-108.
2. Aguilera-Huertas, J., Parras-Alcántara, L., González-Rosado, M., & Lozano-García, B. (2024). Intercropping in rainfed Mediterranean olive groves contributes to improving soil quality and soil organic carbon storage. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 361, 108826.
3. Almagro, M., Díaz-Pereira, E., Boix-Fayos, C., Zornoza, R., Sánchez-Navarro, V., Re, P., ... & Martínez-Mena, M. (2023). The combination of crop diversification and no tillage enhances key soil quality parameters related to soil functioning without compromising crop yields in a low-input rainfed almond orchard under semiarid Mediterranean conditions. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 345, 108320.
4. Andrés, P., Rosell-Melé, A., Colomer-Ventura, F., Deneff, K., Cotrufo, M. F., Riba, M., & Alcañiz, J. M. (2019). Belowground biota responses to maize biochar addition to the soil of a Mediterranean vineyard. *Science of the total environment*, 660, 1522-1532.
5. Arshad, M., Khedher, K. M., Ayed, H., Mouldi, A., Moghanm, F. S., El Ouni, M. H., ... & Abdel Zaher, M. (2020). Effects of land use and cultivation histories on the distribution of soil organic carbon stocks in the area of the Northern Nile Delta in Egypt. *Carbon Management*, 11(4), 341-354.
6. Badagliacca, G., Benítez, E., Amato, G., Badalucco, L., Giambalvo, D., Laudicina, V. A., & Ruisi, P. (2018). Long-term no-tillage application increases soil organic carbon, nitrous oxide emissions and faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) yields under rain-fed Mediterranean conditions. *Science of the Total Environment*, 639, 350-359.
7. Badagliacca, G., Benítez, E., Amato, G., Badalucco, L., Giambalvo, D., Laudicina, V. A., & Ruisi, P. (2018). Long-term effects of contrasting tillage on soil organic carbon, nitrous oxide and ammonia emissions in a Mediterranean Vertisol under different crop sequences. *Science of the Total Environment*, 619, 18-27.
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9. Baiano, S., & Morra, L. (2017). Changes in soil organic carbon after five years of biowaste compost application in a Mediterranean vegetable cropping system. *Pedosphere*, 27(2), 328-337.
10. Baiano, S., & Morra, L. (2017). Changes in soil organic carbon after five years of biowaste compost application in a Mediterranean vegetable cropping system. *Pedosphere*, 27(2), 328-337.

11. Barut, Z., & Celik, I. (2017). Tillage effects on some soil physical properties in a semi-arid Mediterranean region of Turkey. *Chemical Engineering Transactions*, 58, 217-222.
12. Bashour, I. I., Al-Ouda, A. S., Kassam, A. H., Bachour, R., Jouni, K., Hansmann, B., & Estephan, C. (2016). An overview of Conservation Agriculture in the dry Mediterranean environments with a special focus on Syria and Lebanon.
13. Begum, K., Zornoza, R., Farina, R., Lemola, R., Álvaro-Fuentes, J., & Cerasuolo, M. (2022). Modeling Soil Carbon Under Diverse Cropping Systems and Farming Management in Contrasting Climatic Regions in Europe. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 10, 819162.
14. Bombino, G., Denisi, P., Gómez, J. A., & Zema, D. A. (2021). Mulching as best management practice to reduce surface runoff and erosion in steep clayey olive groves. *International Soil and Water Conservation Research*, 9(1), 26-36.
15. Brunori, E., Farina, R., & Biasi, R. (2016). Sustainable viticulture: The carbon-sink function of the vineyard agro-ecosystem. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 223, 10-21.
16. Brunori, E., Maesano, M., Moresi, F. V., Matteucci, G., Biasi, R., & Scarascia Mugnozza, G. (2020). The hidden land conservation benefits of olive-based (*Olea europaea* L.) landscapes: An agroforestry investigation in the southern Mediterranean (Calabria region, Italy). *Land degradation & development*, 31(7), 801-815.
17. Cabrera-Pérez, C., Llorens, J., Escola, A., Royo-Esnal, A., & Recasens, J. (2023). Organic mulches as an alternative for under-vine weed management in Mediterranean irrigated vineyards: Impact on agronomic performance. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 145, 126798.
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21. Cardinael, R., Chevallier, T., Barthès, B. G., Saby, N. P., Parent, T., Dupraz, C., ... & Chenu, C. (2015). Impact of alley cropping agroforestry on stocks, forms and spatial distribution of soil organic carbon—A case study in a Mediterranean context. *Geoderma*, 259, 288-299.
22. Cirigliano, P., Cresti, A., Rengo, A., D'Arcangelo, M. E. M., & Brunori, E. (2023). Monitoring of Seasonal Under-Vine CO₂ Effluxes in a Vineyard under Different Fertilization Practices. *Horticulturae*, 9(10), 1107.

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26. Diop, M., Beniaich, A., Cicek, H., Ouabbou, H., Bamouh, A., El Gharras, O., ... & El Mejahed, K. (2024). Short-term residual effects of occasional tillage on crop performance, soil water, and water-use efficiency in a 10-year no-till system under a dry Mediterranean climate. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 8, 1375666.
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Annex 2- Structure of the Database and Included Categories

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	No.	APA	Title	Author(s)	Publishing Date	Link to Source	Cited	Main conclusions
2								
23								

I	J	K	L
Methods Used	Grouped methods	Positive extrenalities of CF	Positive extrenalites indicator

M	N	O	P	Q
Benefits category	Results from Provided Study	Geographical Context	Topography	Precipitation level
Environmental				
Economic				
Social				
GAPS				

R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y
Soil Texture			Texture class	SOC level	Other relevant factors	Grade (1-5)	Comment
Sand %	Silt %	Clay%					
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sand Silt Clay Loam Sandy Loam Clay Loam Silty Loam Sandy Clay Sandy Clay Loam Loamy Sand Silty Clay Loam Silty Clay 				

Annex 3 - Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits

Farmer Survey on Carbon Farming Practices and Co-Benefits

Welcome to the Carbon Farming Med Survey

Thank you for participating in the *Carbon Farming Med* project. Your insights are invaluable in assessing the positive externalities of carbon farming practices in the Mediterranean region.

The *Carbon Farming Med* project supports Mediterranean countries in achieving the EU's 2035 climate goals by promoting climate-neutral and sustainable agriculture. Through the development of a carbon farming framework, the creation of a Mediterranean carbon credits market, and the implementation of regenerative practices, the project aims to make carbon farming a viable and profitable business model for farmers.

This survey aims to collect information about your farm, the practices you implement, and the benefits and challenges you experience. Your responses will contribute to a better understanding of how carbon farming can enhance environmental sustainability, economic viability, and social well-being across the region.

Instructions:

The survey should take approximately **20-30 minutes** to complete. Your responses will be kept confidential and used solely for research purposes. Please answer all questions to the best of your ability. If you have any questions or need assistance, feel free to contact the research team.

Confidentiality Statement:

Your responses will be kept confidential and will be used only for the purposes of the CARBON FARMING MED project. Individual data will not be shared with third parties without your consent. If you have any questions or need further assistance, please contact:

Research Team Contact:

Name: [Ema Midžić, Elma Porča]

Email: [ema.midzic@cener21.ba, elma.porca@cener21.ba]

I have read and understood the information provided above. I consent to participate in this survey.

Answer options (Multiple choice):

- Yes → **Continue to the next section**
- No → **Submit form**

Section A: Farm and Farmer Profile

1. Farmer Information:

a. **Name:**

b. **Age:**

c. **Gender:**

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

d. **Education Level:**

- No formal education
- Primary education
- Secondary education
- Vocational training
- University degree
- Other (please specify):

SECTION B: Farm Information:

a. **Farm Name:**

b. **Location:**

- Country:
- The exact location of your farm (e.g., GPS coordinates, or address):
- Region/Province:
- Nearest Town/City:

c. **Farm size**

What is the total size of your farm, in hectares?

- Less than 0.5 hectare
- 0.5–1 hectare

- 1–5 hectares
- 5–20 hectares
- 20–100 hectares
- More than 100 hectares
- Other:

d. Farm Type (select all that apply):

- Arable crops
- Permanent crops (e.g., orchards, vineyards)
- Livestock farming
- Mixed farming
- Agroforestry
- Other (please specify):

e. Farm management

How many years have you been managing this farm?

What is the ownership status of the farm?

- Owned
- Leased
- Family-owned
- Cooperative
- Other (please specify):

SECTION C: Current Farming Practices

Agricultural Practices Implemented (select all that apply)

- Conventional tillage
- Conservation agriculture
- Organic farming system
- Crop rotation
- Cover cropping
- Smart irrigation
- Regenerative agriculture
- Use of organic fertilisers
- Use of chemical fertilisers
- Use of chemical pesticides/herbicides

- Intercropping
- Agroforestry systems
- Livestock integration
- Precision agriculture
- Plasticulture (use of plastic mulch or tunnels)
- Mulching
- Integrated pest management (IPM)
- Other: _____

How often do you apply the following carbon farming practices on your farm? (Likert scale: 1 = Never, 2 = Rarely, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Always)

- Use of organic amendments
- Reducing soil disturbance
- Cover crops
- Agroforestry practices
- Enhanced agronomic management
- Conversion to perennial woody plantations
- Sustainable water management
- Other (please specify):

Enter the area of the farm that is being managed using carbon farming practices, in hectares.

How important are the following factors in your decision to adopt carbon farming practices?" (Please rate each factor on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = Not at all important and 5 = Extremely important.)

- Environmental sustainability
 - Economic benefits
 - Comply with environmental regulations or standards
 - Soil health and fertility improvement
 - Increase yield or productivity
 - Water conservation
 - Biodiversity enhancement
-
- Market demand
 - Reduce input costs (e.g., fertilisers, water)
 - Adapt to climate change and drought
 - Access to subsidies or financial incentives
 - Participation in a carbon credit or certification scheme

- Influence from other farmers or farmer networks
 - Personal interest
-

Section C: Environmental Co-Benefits

1. Soil Health Improvement:

a. Have you observed changes in soil quality since implementing carbon farming practices?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please indicate the changes observed (select all that apply):

- Increased soil organic matter
- Improved soil structure
- Enhanced nutrient availability
- Increased water retention
- Reduced soil erosion
- Other (please specify):

2. Biodiversity Enhancement:

a. Have you noticed changes in biodiversity on your farm?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please indicate the changes observed (select all that apply):

- Increase in pollinators (e.g., bees, butterflies)
- Increase in beneficial insects
- Greater variety of plant species
- Increase in bird populations
- Presence of wildlife
- Other (please specify):

3. Water Management:

a. Have your water use practices changed since adopting carbon farming methods?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please describe the changes (select all that apply):

- Improved water retention in soil
- Reduced irrigation needs
- Enhanced drought resilience
- Improved drainage
- Other (please specify):

4. Reduction in Chemical Inputs:

a. Have you reduced the use of chemical fertilisers and pesticides?

- Yes
- No

b. If you have reduced fertiliser usage as part of your farming practices, by approximately what percentage have you reduced it? Please provide a percentage (e.g., 20%, 50%). Additionally, please explain why this reduction was achieved.

c. If you have reduced the use of pesticides/herbicides as part of your farming practices, by approximately what percentage have you reduced it? Please provide a percentage (e.g., 30%, 60%). Additionally, please explain why and how this reduction was achieved.

Section D: Economic Co-Benefits

1. Crop Yields:

a. Have your crop yields changed since implementing carbon farming practices?

- Increased
- Decreased
- No significant change

b. If increased or decreased, please estimate the percentage change:

- Percentage change: _____%**

2. Cost Savings:

a. Have you experienced cost savings in farm operations?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, in which areas? (select all that apply):

- Reduced expenditure on chemical fertilisers
- Reduced expenditure on pesticides/herbicides
- Lower water usage costs
- Reduced fuel consumption
- Other (please specify):

3. Additional Revenue Streams:

a. Are you participating in any carbon credit programmes or receiving payments for ecosystem services?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please provide details:

- Type of program:**
- Annual revenue generated (€):**

4. Market Access:

a. Has adopting carbon farming practices affected your market access?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please explain:

- Access to premium markets
- Better prices for products
- New customer segments
- Certifications achieved (e.g., organic, sustainable)
- Other (please specify):

1. Employment and Labour:

a. Has the implementation of carbon farming practices affected labour requirements on your farm?

- Increased labour needs
- Decreased labour needs
- No significant change

b. If increased, have you hired additional workers?

- Yes
- No

2. Community Impact:

a. Have your farming practices had any impact on the local community?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please describe (select all that apply):

- Job creation
- Knowledge sharing and education
- Collaboration with other farmers
- Improved local food security
- Other (please specify):

3. Quality of Life:

a. Have the changes in your farming practices affected your quality of life or that of your family?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please explain:

- Increased income stability
- Better work-life balance
- Improved health due to reduced chemical exposure
- Greater satisfaction from sustainable farming

- Other (please specify):
-

Section F: Challenges and Support

1. Challenges Faced:

a. What challenges have you encountered in implementing carbon farming practices? (select all that apply):

- Lack of knowledge or technical expertise
- Initial investment costs
- Labour requirements
- Market barriers
- Regulatory hurdles
- Climate variability
- Limited access to equipment or technology
- Other (please specify):

2. Support Received:

a. Have you received any support to implement carbon farming practices?

- Yes
- No

b. If yes, please specify the type of support:

- Technical training or extension services
- Financial subsidies or grants
- Access to equipment
- Participation in cooperative or farmer groups
- Other (please specify):

3. Information Sources:

a. Where do you obtain information about carbon farming practices? (select all that apply):

- Government agencies

- Agricultural extension services
- Farmer associations or cooperatives
- Academic institutions
- Online resources
- Workshops or training sessions
- Other farmers
- Other (please specify):

Section G: Perceptions and Future Plans

1. Overall Satisfaction:

a. How satisfied are you with the outcomes of implementing carbon farming practices on your farm?

- Very satisfied
- Satisfied
- Neutral
- Unsatisfied
- Very unsatisfied

2. Future Plans:

a. Do you plan to continue or expand carbon farming practices on your farm?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

b. Please explain your decision:

3. Recommendations:

a. Would you recommend carbon farming practices to other farmers?

- Yes
- No

b. Please explain your answer:

Section H: Additional Comments

1. Please share any additional comments or suggestions regarding carbon farming practices and their impacts:

Thank you for your valuable contribution!

Annex 4- Additional Literature

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